

Heldere blik op troebel estuarium (HBOTE)

Technical report fase 2

Part of eindrapport Fase 2

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Technical Report

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Abbreviation	Explanation
AC	Atmospheric correction
ACOLITE	Atmospheric correction of Operational Land Imager (and MSI)
BBM	Benthic biomass
C2RCC	Case-2 Regional / Coast Colour Processor
CDOM	Coloured dissolved organic matter
CHL	Chlorophyll-a (chlorophyll-a)
COAH	Copernicus Open Access Hub
CODA	Copernicus Online Data Access
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
GHRSTT	Group for High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature
GoF	Goodness of Fit
IOP	Inherent Optical Property
LST	Land surface temperature
MODIS	Moderate-resolution imaging spectroradiometer
MSI	Multispectral Instrument onboard of Sentinel 2
OC5	Five channel chlorophyll concentration algorithm
OLCI	Ocean and Land Colour Instrument onboard of Sentinel 3
OLI	Operational Land Imager onboard of Landsat 8
PAR	Photosynthetically active radiation
S2	Sentinel 2
S3	Sentinel 3
SLSTR	Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer onboard of Sentinel 3
SNAP	Sentinel Application Platform

SPM	(Total) Suspended particulate matter
SST	Sea surface temperature

1 Scope

The project HBOTE ('Heldere blik op troebel estuarium', which translates as 'Clear view on a turbid estuary') demonstrates the feasibility to set up an Earth Observation (EO) based service to monitor parameters which are required as input for primary production estimation in the Dollard estuary. The project was implemented in the framework of the SBIR programme by Water Insight (WI) and ITC of the University of Twente (ITC). The end user of the products is Rijkswaterstaat (RWS), while SBIR is funded by the Netherlands Space Office (NSO).

For the aims, social context, technical and financial feasibility, a summary of the results and the conclusions of the project we refer to the final report of phase 2: 'HBOTE Eindrapport fase 2' (in Dutch). This technical report contains supplementary material, including an introduction to optical remote sensing methods for water quality parameters, a description of the satellite and in situ data used in the study, the processing methods, results and conclusion per parameter as well as overall conclusions and recommendations.

1.1 Confidentiality

This technical report is added as an annex to the final report phase 2. The original of this report was confidential.

Adjustments between the original version and this public version:

- Addition on page 11 [marked in blue]
- Figure 6 and description relating to this figure. Original figure was taken from a not public source.
- Figure 7: added reference
- Removed one line on page 105 which was not relevant for the technical conclusions
- Removed two lines on page 109 which was not relevant for the technical conclusions
- Page 113: added acknowledgement. This made the next pages to move 1 page each.

2 Introduction to remote sensing of water parameters

There are many substances that give colour to the water. We usually describe them in categories (see Figure 1):

- Algae pigments: in diatoms, green algae, bluegreen algae (cyanobacteria) and others
- Sediments: silt, sands of many different colours (ranging from white to red/brown to almost black)
- Coloured Dissolved Organic Matter (CDOM, humic acids)
- Anything else that gives colour (bottom sediments, water plants, coloured minerals in mine tailing ponds, etc.)

The color of water reveals its contents

- Most algae appear green due to chlorophyll
- In most coastal waters algae look brown due to additional pigments such as fucoxanthin
- Sediment reflects and is therefore bright
- Cyanobacteria look blue-green
- ...and so on

Figure 1: The colour of water as caused by optical active components

The categories are more or less related to some “ecological water parameters” that are generally accepted measurements (Figure 2):

- Chlorophyll-a (as proxy for phytoplankton biomass)
- Total Suspended Solids (Seston dry weight): anything that remains on a filter
- The Coloured fraction of the Dissolved Organic Matter (CDOM): anything that passes through a filter

Phytoplankton ('algae', including cyanobacteria)

Total Suspended Matter (TSM)
also called
Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM)

Water

Coloured Dissolved
Organic Matter (CDOM)

Figure 2: Categories of optical active components in water.

The substances change the colour of water by absorbing parts of the spectrum (algae absorb blue and red light for photosynthesis) and/or by reflecting (backscattering) parts of the spectrum.

Water itself is a strong absorber of red and NIR light and backscatters (reflects) blue light, hence its natural blue colour. In clear waters light can penetrate the water column to large depths. In very turbid waters like the Dutch Waddenzee this can be limited to decimetres or even centimetres (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Light penetration in clear and slightly turbid waters
 (<http://www.union.edu/PUBLIC/GEODEPT/hollocher/kth/illustrations>)

The total effect of all absorption (a) and backscattering (b_b) is explained by the basic equation:

$$Rrs = f \frac{b_b}{a+b_b}$$

The intensity of the observed reflectance spectrum (Rrs) increases with increased backscattering and decreases with increased absorption. The b_b term under the line corrects for the increased pathlength under water (f is a proportionality function). Both absorption and backscattering can have prominent spectral features.

The optical properties (absorption and scattering) of optically active water constituents are related to their biochemical characteristics by means of physical laws, whereby the concentration can be inferred from the magnitude of absorption and /or scattering. These optical properties are therefore inherent to the constituents as they are also independent of the viewing-illumination geometry, commonly referred to as Inherent Optical Properties (IOPs).

Figure 4: An example of an SIOP, namely the absorption spectra of the normalized to the concentration Chlorophyll-a, -b and accessory pigments (carotenoids) extracted in a solution (up). Bottom: PAR action spectrum of an isolated chloroplast (https://forums.saltwaterfish.com/data/b/b7/b70ee1c4_450px-Par_action_spectrum.gif)

Figure 4 illustrates the absorption of some major phytoplankton pigments as examples of IOPs. In the Bottom graph an example is given in what spectral range phytoplankton uses the available light for photosynthesis. This graph is also used to illustrate the concept of PAR: Photosynthetic Available Radiation which will be further discussed in section 0.

The light that is not reflected back to the surface is absorbed by the water and its components. That property is usually measured as the attenuation coefficient (K_d) or approximated by the Secchi disk depth or the turbidity.

The measurement of colour is done with a spectrometer. The result of the measurement is the amount of light (intensity) reflected by an object (waterbody) per unit of wavelength. Figure 5 shows a series of such graphs produced by a computer program that simulates the effect of several combinations of absorption and (back)scattering on perceived water colour.

Figure 5: Simulated colour spectra of water as function of changes in the concentrations of optical active components [Simulated with Bi-Opti]

Here we see the following combined effects:

- CDOM lowers the reflectance spectrum in the blue wavelengths because of blue absorption. We see CDOM as a brownish substance because of the lack of blue light.
- Dips in the spectrum around 490 and 675 nm are caused by the absorption of Chlorophyll-a
- A dip in the spectrum caused by the cyanobacteria pigment Phycocyanin between 600 and 650 nm, peaking at 620 nm
- Differences in the amplitude of the spectrum (run 1 is low, run 10 is high) caused by an increase in sediment particles in the water (acting over the whole spectral range). The particles reflect light back from the water before it is absorbed: so backscattering is making the water perceivably lighter.
- Water absorption lowers the reflectance above 700 nm considerably.

Attempts have been made to categorize global waters based on their spectra. An example is given in Figure 6 where we see the following:

1. Brown line: this could be estuarine water. strong absorptions in the blue and red regions indicating a mix of CDOM and Chlorophyll-a absorptions combined with a peak in green reflectance (550 nm) indicating backscattering from sediments.
2. Purple line: deep clear lake water. Less absorption in the Blue, less pronounced Chlorophyll-a absorption features (but still visible around 490 and 665)
3. Bright green: nutrient rich lake water. Pronounced Chl-a and phycocyanin absorption dips.

Figure 6: General classes of inland water spectra. Image is part of Figure 2 from Eleveld, M.A.; Ruescas, A.B.; Hommersom, A.; Moore, T.S.; Peters, S.W.M.; Brockmann, C. *An Optical Classification Tool for Global Lake Waters*. *Remote Sens.* 2017, 9, 420. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9050420>

The Dutch Waddenzee would qualify as estuarine/Coastal waters in this classification. In this area there are many processes leading to water colour and water turbidity as illustrated by Figure 7:

Figure 7: Processes governing the concentration of optical active components in the Wadden Sea [image: Hommersom et al, 2019]

In a small area we can witness simultaneously processes as: exchange of water with the North Sea and

rivers, phytoplankton development in deeper waters, turbidity gradients caused by resuspension and a separation of fast flowing waters (channels) and slowly moving waters (mudflats) all governed by the tide.

Example of a satellite image of the Wadden Sea (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Example of a Sentinel 2 image of the Wadden Sea

Satellites observe only parts of the spectrum (spectral bands) that are designed to capture the prominent spectral absorption and backscattering features caused by the optical active components including water and features that help to characterise the optical properties of the atmosphere between the satellite and the surface. A recent study by Dekker et al., 2018 produced a comprehensive overview of observable spectral features in water and a table (table 2.2) that indicates the optimal spectral bands for a “aquatic ecosystem earth observing system”.

Sensors on earth observing (EO) satellites measure, in addition to the water colour, the atmospheric layer between the sensor and the water target, affecting thereby the quality of the sensed signal (Su et al. 2011). In the most negative case the complete signal is blocked by clouds but often haze, water vapour, ozone, trace gasses etcetera work together to attenuate the signal before it arrives at the satellite.

Figure 9 shows how the colour of the water is affected by the atmosphere, which could be up to 80% of the

recorded signals by earth observing sensors. This atmospheric signal, if not corrected, propagates large errors to EO-derived water quality variables, e.g. haze could mistakenly be interpreted as turbidity. The standard procedure to retrieve the concentration of water constituents from satellite data passes, therefore, through three stages that are critical for accurate estimation: i-) atmospheric correction; ii-) retrieving the inherent optical properties (IOPs) of water constituents; and iii-) estimate the concentration of water constituents from their retrieved IOPs.

Figure 9: Schematic diagram of the different processes that contribute to the signal observed above inland waters. (From Su et al., 2011, Chapter 2.14.9: Optical RS for Water Quality in Inland and Coastal Waters in Treaties on Water Science, Elsevier 2011 Editor P. Wilderer)

3 Overview of Earth Observation data and processing methods

3.1 Satellite data used

When using optical satellite data there is always a trade-off between spatial, temporal, spectral and radiometric resolution, and cost. The spectral resolution determines which parameters can be detected by a sensor, the spatial and temporal resolution determine the monitoring capability. However, this trade-off is continuously shifting, as detector sensitivity is increasing, and newer sensors have in general a higher radiometric sensitivity than older ones.

The spectral resolution determines which water quality parameters can be determined how accurately. While some water constituents such as TSM influence a large part of the spectrum and are therefore in principle detectable by sensors with relatively broad spectral bands, other constituents such as phycocyanin (a pigment of cyanobacteria (blue-green algae)) show distinct features only in a very narrow part of the spectrum, which only sensors with a dedicated band set can pick up.

The difference between the sensors is illustrated in Figure 10, which shows that the low-resolution Sentinel-3 OLCI has much narrower spectral bands than the medium-resolution Sentinel-2 MSI and Landsat-8 OLI, which can serve to pick up the specific signals of water constituents such as chlorophyll-a (as discussed in chapter 2).

Figure 10: Spectral bands of the optical sensors used in this study

In phase 1, the feasibility study, HBOTE studied three Earth Observation (EO) datasets:

- A low-resolution dataset with a high frequency, derived from specific 'ocean colour' sensors. This dataset will serve to analyse the variation in time and space of the required parameters on a large scale.

- A medium-resolution dataset with a medium frequency derived from multispectral sensors. With this dataset we evaluate the (changes in) spatial variability of the processes in the water and on the tidal flats.
- A high-resolution data set with a low frequency, derived from high resolution sensor(s). This dataset evaluated the high spatial variability of the benthic microalgae (not used in phase 2).

A conclusion of the feasibility study was that the added value of the high-resolution data set is limited while the effort to process these data is high, therefore, in the demonstration study, we only continued with the low and medium resolution datasets. For example, Figure 11 illustrates that the high resolution (in this case: RapidEye with 5m resolution) data does not offer a lot more detail than the medium resolution (Sentinel-2 MSI with 10m resolution) data. Overall, the patterns in the two images are similar, with the values of the high resolution images being slightly higher.

Figure 11: Comparison of high resolution and medium resolution NDVI data (area Leybucht)

Data from the following satellite sensors were used in this demonstration study:

Sentinel-3 OLCI

Sentinel 3 is the dedicated water colour observation satellite of the Copernicus programme, operated jointly by ESA and EUMETSAT. It is a constellation of two satellites, both orbiting Earth at an altitude of 814.5 km, to optimise coverage. Sentinel-3A was launched in 2/2016 and Sentinel-3B in 4/2018. They have a design life of at least 7 years, with the follow up satellites 3C/3D already being built.

The Ocean and Land Colour Instrument (OLCI) is based on heritage from Envisat’s Medium Resolution

Imaging Spectrometer and features 21 distinct bands between 400 - 1020 nm tuned to specific ocean colour, vegetation and atmospheric correction measurement requirements (see Table 1). It has a spatial resolution of 300 m for all measurements and a swath width of 1270 km. Depending on the instrument, Sentinel-3A and Sentinel-3B provide global coverage every two days, but thanks to overlap between swaths from adjacent orbits, the revisit in the Dutch coastal waters is in fact daily. The data are processed systematically and usually available for users within 3–48 hours after sensing.

Table 1: Band characteristics of the SENTINEL-3 Ocean and Land Colour Instrument (OLCI)

Band	λ centre (nm)	Width (nm)	Function
Oa1	400	15	Aerosol correction, improved water constituent retrieval
Oa2	412.5	10	Yellow substance and detrital pigments (turbidity)
Oa3	442.5	10	Chl absorption max., biogeochemistry, vegetation
Oa4	490	10	High Chl, other pigments
Oa5	510	10	Chl, sediment, turbidity, red tide
Oa6	560	10	Chlorophyll reference (Chl minimum)
Oa7	620	10	Sediment loading
Oa8	665	10	Chl (2nd Chl abs. max.), sediment, yellow substance/vegetation
Oa9	673.75	7.5	For improved fluorescence retrieval and to better account for the smile* effect together with the bands 665 and 680 nm
Oa10	681.25	7.5	Chl fluorescence peak, red edge
Oa11	708.75	10	Chl fluorescence baseline, red edge transition
Oa12	753.75	7.5	O2 absorption/clouds, vegetation
Oa13	761.25	2.5	O2 absorption band/aerosol corr.
Oa14	764.375	3.75	Atmospheric correction
Oa15	767.5	2.5	O2A used for cloud top pressure, fluorescence over land
Oa16	778.75	15	Atmos. corr./aerosol corr.
Oa17	865	20	Atmos. corr./aerosol corr., clouds, pixel co-registration
Oa18	885	10	Water vapour absorption reference band. Common reference band with SLSTR instrument. Vegetation monitoring
Oa19	900	10	Water vapour absorption/vegetation monitoring (max. reflectance)
Oa20	940	20	Water vapour absorption, atmos./aerosol corr.

Oa21	1 020	40	Atmos./aerosol corr.
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*Differences between the satellite’s optical modules which introduce variations between the spectral channel’s central wavelength and slight misalignments create the “smile” effect.

Sentinel-2 MSI

Sentinel 2 is the dedicated land observation satellite of the Copernicus programme, operated by ESA. It is a constellation of two satellites, both orbiting Earth at an altitude of 786 km, to optimise coverage. Together they cover all Earth’s land surfaces, large islands, inland and coastal waters every five days at the equator. Sentinel-2A was launched in 6/2015 and Sentinel-2B in 3/2017. They have a design life of at least 7 years, with the follow up satellites 2C/2D already being built.

The Multispectral imager (MSI) covering 13 spectral bands (443 nm–2190 nm) with a swath width of 290 km and spatial resolutions of 10 m (4 visible and near-infrared bands, see Table 2), 20 m (6 red-edge/shortwave-infrared bands, see Table 3) and 60 m (3 atmospheric correction bands, see Table 4) is based on well-established heritage from France’s SPOT missions and the US Landsat satellites. The data are processed systematically and usually available for users within 3–48 hours after sensing.

Table 2: 10 m Spatial Resolution Bands and associated Signal to Noise ratio (SNR) of S2 MSI

Band number	Central wavelength (nm)	Bandwidth (nm)	Range/purpose
2	490	65	Blue
3	560	35	Green
4	665	30	Red
8	842	115	Vegetation red edge

Table 3: 20 metre Spatial Resolution Bands and associated Signal to Noise ratio (SNR) of S2 MSI

Band number	Central wavelength (nm)	Bandwidth (nm)	Range/purpose
5	705	15	Vegetation red edge
6	740	15	Vegetation red edge
7	783	20	Vegetation red edge
8a	865	20	Vegetation red edge
11	1 610	90	SWIR

12	2 190	180	SWIR
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Table 4: 60 metre Spatial Resolution Bands and associated Signal to Noise ratio (SNR) of S2 MSI

Band number	Central wavelength (nm)	Bandwidth (nm)	Range/purpose
1	443	20	Coastal aerosol
9	945	20	Water vapour
10	1 375	30	SWIR - Cirrus

Landsat-8 OLI and TIRS

Landsat 8 is a collaboration between NASA and the U.S. Geological Survey, providing moderate-resolution (15 m–100 m, depending on spectral frequency) measurements of the Earth’s terrestrial and polar regions in the visible, near-infrared, short wave infrared, and thermal infrared in 11 spectral bands (see Table 5). Landsat 8 carries two push-broom instruments: The Operational Land Imager (OLI) and the Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS). Landsat 8 provides continuity with the more than 40-year long Landsat land imaging data set. Landsat 8 was launched in 2/2013 and has a minimum design life of 5.25 years. Its successor Landsat-9 is expected to be launched in 2020. The revisit time of Landsat 8 is 16 days. Data collected are available to download at no charge from within 24 hours of acquisition.

Table 5: Landsat 8 OLI and TIRS spectral bands

Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) and Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) images consist of nine spectral bands with a spatial resolution of 30 meters for Bands 1 to 7 and 9. New band 1 (ultra-blue) is useful for coastal and aerosol studies. New band 9 is useful for cirrus cloud detection. The resolution for Band 8 (panchromatic) is 15 meters. Thermal bands 10 and 11 are useful in providing more accurate surface temperatures and are collected at 100 meters. Approximate scene size is 170 km north-south by 183 km east-west (106 mi by 114 mi).

Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) and Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) Launched February 11, 2013	Bands	Wavelength (micrometers)	Resolution (meters)
	Band 1 - Coastal aerosol	0.43 - 0.45	30
	Band 2 - Blue	0.45 - 0.51	30
	Band 3 - Green	0.53 - 0.59	30
	Band 4 - Red	0.64 - 0.67	30
	Band 5 - Near Infrared (NIR)	0.85 - 0.88	30
	Band 6 - SWIR 1	1.57 - 1.65	30
	Band 7 - SWIR 2	2.11 - 2.29	30
	Band 8 - Panchromatic	0.50 - 0.68	15
	Band 9 - Cirrus	1.36 - 1.38	30
	Band 10 - Thermal Infrared (TIRS) 1	10.60 - 11.19	100 * (30)
Band 11 - Thermal Infrared (TIRS) 2	11.50 - 12.51	100 * (30)	

* TIRS bands are acquired at 100 meter resolution, but are resampled to 30 meter in delivered data product.

The data from the above-mentioned satellites are retrieved as level 1b data and further processed in house with specialised algorithms to yield the requested water and land surface products. For two products (low resolution SST and PAR), however, we retrieved the processed data from third parties as these are well-developed and validated products that are applicable in the study area:

Photosynthetically active radiation

PAR data are derived from the EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility (OSI SAF) project’s Surface Solar Irradiance (SSI) daily dataset based on the 0.6 µm visible channel of SEVIRI on board the geostationary satellite Meteosat (OSISAF 2018).

Sea Surface Temperature (low resolution)

The low resolution SST data is retrieved from the Group for High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature (GHR SST) Level 4 sea surface temperature analysis product (JPL OurOcean Project 2010)). This daily 1km product is provided on an operational basis by the JPL OurOcean group. It uses satellite data from sensors that include the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR), the Advanced Along Track Scanning

Radiometer (AATSR), the Spinning Enhanced Visible and Infrared Imager (SEVIRI), the Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer-EOS (AMSRE), the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission Microwave Imager (TMI), the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) Imager, the Multi-Functional Transport Satellite 1R (MTSAT-1R) radiometer, and in situ data from drifting and moored buoys.

3.2 Processing methods

The satellite data is processed according to the scheme given in Figure 12, with specific algorithms per sensor and parameter.

Figure 12: Processing chain for EO data in HBOTE

In Table 6 (low resolution) and Table 7 (medium resolution) an overview is provided of which satellite sensor data is included, and which algorithms were used for processing of this data. These algorithms were applied to derive the final products. During the feasibility study (phase 1) and this demonstration project (phase 2) a number of different algorithms were tested and compared. In this report we present the results based on the algorithms that were assessed to work best in the Eems-Dollard region.

Table 6: Low resolution dataset

Parameter	Sensor(s) / source	Spatial resolution	Atmospheric correction	Algorithm	Comments
SST	Multiple sensors/ GHRSSST	1km		GHRSSST	Interpolated in case of clouds
PAR	SEVIRI / METEOSAT	0.05 degree		OSISAF	
SPM	OLCI / CODA	300m	Aug. C2RCC-augmented	Nechad 2010	
CDOM			Aug. C2RCC-augmented	C2RCC	
Kd			Aug. C2RCC-augmented	Gons 1998	
CHL			Aug. C2RCC-augmented	Gons 2005	
LST	TERRA / MODIS	1km	MODIS standard	MODIS standard LST product	
Sediment type	OLCI / CODA	300m	OLCI standard	WI, this report	
NDVI			OLCI standard	Standard defintion	
BBM			OLCI standard	Kromkamp 2006	

Table 7: Medium resolution dataset

Parameter	Sensor(s) / source	Spatial resolution	Atmospheric correction	Algorithms tested	notes
SST	OLI / USGS	100m	Barsi 2005	Barsi 2005	

SPM	MSI / COAH	10m	C2X	Nechad 2010	
CDOM			C2X	C2X	Experimental product
Kd			C2X	Gons 1998	
CHL			C2X	Gons 2005	
LST	OLI / USGS	100m	Barsi 2005	Barsi 2005	
Sediment type	MSI / COAH	10m		WI, this report	
NDVI				Standard definition	
BBM				Kromkamp 2006	

The processing is largely automated, based on tools such as SNAP, in combination with WI’s own Python and C scripts in a flexible and scalable processing environment. Details of C2RCC and C2X algorithm can be found in Brockmann et al, 2016.

The effect of bottom visibility

The TSM and Chl-a algorithms used in this study do not take into account that part of the observed reflectance might be generated by the bottom. If there is bottom visibility this theoretically has two effects:

- 1) the reflectance amplitude is elevated, especially if the bottom is sandy and bright
- 2) If there is vegetation covering the bottom one would observe additional chlorophyll absorption that should not be attributed to algae

So in the first case TSM algorithms will provide an overestimation. In the second case Chlorophyll-a algorithms might produce an overestimation and possibly also the TSM might be overestimated, depending on the vegetation density and absorption characteristics.

Our selected TSM algorithm (Nechad, 2010) has a linear sensitivity to bottom visibility. We attempt to minimise this sensitivity by choosing a wavelength that is linearly related to TSM concentrations, not sensitive to Chl-a and CDOM absorption and moderately sensitive to water absorption itself. The wavelength we choose to operate the TSM algorithm on is 704 nm. At this wavelength the water absorption is noticeable: in clear waters the Kd would be around 0.6-0.8 at 700 nm and 2-3 at 700 nm when the water becomes more turbid (Simon and Shanmugan, 2013). This leads (at 700 nm) to an optical

depth of 1.5 m (clear waters) to less than 0.5 m, depending on the turbidity of the water. The Nechad TSM algorithm can also be operated at lower wavelengths (with different coefficients) which would make it more suitable for less turbid waters with much higher optical depths.

Our selected Chl-a algorithm would be most sensitive to the visibility of green vegetation on the bottom seen through shallow water that is clear enough to allow the reflected light signal to reach the surface. The Gons algorithm operates on the wavelengths 665, 704 and around 750 nm. This algorithm, using the red Chl-a absorption peak, was specifically designed for turbid eutrophic waters. In clear waters the K_d at 665 is around 0.3-0.4 leading to a maximal optical depth of around 3 meters. The reference bands at 704 and 750 nm are less sensitive to bottom visibility because of the high water absorption in that spectral region.

Given the fact that MWTL observed K_dPAR values in the area start at 0.5 and go up to 3.5-4, one may conclude that in general it is probable that TSM and Chl-a estimates are not very highly affected by bottom visibility. An exception would e.g. be the situation where thin water sheets are covering mudflats covered with benthic flora.

So for this area one could conclude that the approach and products are probably not strongly affected by bottom visibility at low tide and high tide situations. The effect of bottom visibility, in future, needs further assessment at locations/times where thin water layers are covering the surface temporarily.

Differences in the real Chl-a absorption peak and the satellite band settings

Simis and Kauko (2012) mention as main absorption bands for Chl-a 440 and 675 nm. Gons (1999) takes 672 nm as the Chl-a absorption peak close enough to the true maximum at 675 nm. The CEOS report (Dekker et al., 2018) recommends for a dedicated multispectral instrument to have a band peaking at 676 nm for the Red Chl-a in vivo absorption maximum. The MERIS Chl-a absorption band is centered around 665 nm. Sentinel-3 Chl-a absorption bands is 665 (10 nm wide) for MERIS compatibility. A band centered at 673.75 nm (7.5 nm wide) was added for better fluorescence retrieval and Sentinel -2 Chl-a absorption band is: 665 nm (30 nm wide). The main argument to center the satellite bands around 665 nm is, that positioning it around 676 nm could be contaminated by Chl-a fluorescence in hyper-eutrophic systems (Mishra&Mishra 2014).

3.3 Data availability

One year of data is produced as example dataset. A year provides the best insight in seasonal effects, which determine primary production to a large extent. The chosen period is 2017. This choice is based on the availability of Sentinel-3 OLCI data, which has spectral bands that are very suitable for retrieval of coastal water quality parameters.

Figure 14 provides an overview of the data which were available and processed for each sensor over the chosen year. The colour indicated the fraction of the area covered. For the water parameters, the fraction cover is based on a shapefile of the study area. For the tidal flats parameters, an aggregate image was created with all pixels that are at one time visible for Sentinel-2, and these maps was used as reference for the fractional cover. The masks used for determining the fractional cover are shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Masks used to determine the fractional cover of the study area for water layers (left) and tidal flats layers (right)

The nominal overpass frequency of Sentinel-2 is 10 days (with one satellite) and 5 days (with both satellites), of Sentinel-3 at least every two days (with one satellite) and daily (with both satellites) and of Landsat-8 16 days. Sentinel 2B was launched in March 2017 with data originally becoming available in October 2017 (with the data from the commissioning phase partly becoming available in retrospect), hence the increase in available images in the second half of the year. However, a limiting factor for actual data availability is cloud cover, the effect of which is clearly visible in Figure 14.

It should be noted that for grainsize and medium resolution temperature only selected images were processed. For grainsize, the assumption was that this parameter is not quite as variable as the others, therefore it is not necessary to monitor it on a weekly to monthly basis. For the medium resolution sea and land surface temperature, a preselection of relatively cloud-free images was made as the processing is not fully automated. Also, for the first few months of 2017, for S2 for all parameters completely cloudy images were discarded before processing. Later, all images were processed and empty results were discarded, but are still recorded in Figure 14.

Low resolution PAR and SST show very high availability due to the nature of the datasets: PAR is derived from the geostationary satellite Meteosat, offering continuous coverage of the study area, albeit at low resolution. Also, PAR can also be determined in cloudy conditions. Therefore, the coverage of this dataset is complete. SST is a dataset based on spatial and temporal interpolation of a number of different sensors, and therefore also offers full coverage. For the other datasets, the coverage is a combination of the satellite characteristics (overpass frequency) and atmospheric conditions (cloud cover hampering the acquisition of surface data from optical and thermal images).

Figure 14: Overview of the availability and fractional cover of the study area of the different satellite data. Low resolution: 300m – 8km, Medium resolution 10m – 100m.

4 Overview of validation data and methods

Validation is the action of checking or proving the validity or accuracy of satellite products. It measures the correctness and meaningfulness of derived values against measured quantities. A proper method for accuracy control for EO-based products is essential for the development of operational water quality services. We have therefore collected a large in situ data set to perform these analyses. From these in-situ data, pairs of ‘matchups’ were selected. Matchup is defined here as a pair of in situ measurement (concentration of a water constituent or a spectral measurement) measured in the same time span (varies between couple of hours to minutes) and location as a satellite image. The match up data set is the verification ‘ground truth’ against which the EO products are validated.

Because the largest amount of light that is captured by satellite sensors is reflected by the atmosphere (e.g. Figure 9), it is essential to remove the atmospheric effects from the signal (atmospheric correction). The accuracy of water quality products is largely (>95%) dependent on the atmospheric correction methods and algorithms (Salama and Stein 2009, Salama et al., 2011, Salama 2012). Only in a second step, the concentrations of the parameters can be derived from the atmospherically corrected signal.

Therefore, the validation was split in two levels:

1. inspection of the atmospheric correction and
2. inspection of the uncertainty in water quality products

Validation often uses type II linear-regression, whereby the slope, intercept and determination coefficients (R^2) are estimated between derived and measured values. In addition, the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) is estimated as:

$$MAPE = 100 \times \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} \left\| 1 - \frac{y_i}{x_i} \right\|, \text{ Eq.1}$$

With x_i being the measured value and y_i the derived value. The reason for using mean absolute error (MAE), rather than the well-known root mean square error (RMSE), is that MAE is a more natural measure of average error, and (unlike RMSE) is unambiguous (Willmott and Matsuura, 2005; Pontius et al., 2008). As requested by the scientific advisory of the project, during the end presentation 15 June 2018, we also provide another measure of error, namely the normalized mean absolute error (NMAE), estimated as:

$$NMAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} \left\| \frac{x_i - y_i}{IQR} \right\|, \text{ Eq.2}$$

Whereby the mean absolute error is normalized to IQR interquartile range i.e. the difference between 75th and 25th percentiles, or between upper and lower quartiles (Kokoska and Zwillinger, 2000). For Gaussian distribution the IQR will be equal to 1.349σ , where σ is the standard deviation. However, in the calculation of NMAE, and to avoid the assumption of normally distribution, IQR is computed from the data as the difference between 75th and 25th percentiles.

This measure, NMAE, will be used together with MAPE to report the final accuracy of retrieved concentrations of water quality variables, namely Chlorophyll-a (Chla) and Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM).

These five statistical parameters will be used in this report for validation, i.e. as measures of goodness-of-fit (GoF) between derived and measured variables. High accuracy in the retrieved values yields the following GoF parameters: slope = 1, intercept = 0, $R^2 = 1$ and MAPE = NMAE = 0.

Ad 1. For the verification of the atmospheric correction, matchups between satellite pixels and in-situ reflectance data are needed. Close-range sensors use the same sensing technology as earth-observing satellites with their platforms being just few meters above the water target, in contrast to orbital and geostationary satellites that normally operate at altitudes of ~800 km and ~3600 km, respectively. This low altitude implies that the data acquired by close-range sensors are free of atmospheric influences and can, therefore, be used as benchmark for atmospheric correction and retrieval models. Because there is no spectral data of the study area itself within the period of interest, spectral data from the automated TRiOS sensors at NIOZ (also Wadden Sea) are used.

Ad 2. For the verification of the accuracy of water quality products from EO data, parameters derived from EO data are compared with in-situ data from the match up dataset.

However, by doing this, differences can be caused not only by the parameter retrieval algorithms, but also by errors in the atmospheric correction, or simply by the difference in spatial dimension: in a highly dynamic area like the Ems Dollard estuary concentrations might differ substantially between a point measurement and the average of a pixel size. Therefore, the parameter retrieval algorithms can also be verified on pairs of in situ obtained reflectance data, with simultaneously obtained laboratory data. The advantage is that this kind of dataset is generally larger than the datasets with simultaneous in situ and satellite measurements.

In this report we used a dataset with pairs of in situ optical measurements and laboratory measurements to determine the suitability of algorithms for Chl-a and SPM retrieval. In a next step we verify the performance of these algorithms with pairs of EO and in situ measurements.

A general discussion on validation can be found in the “Eindrapport”, chapter 4 (in Dutch).

4.1 In situ data

The following in-situ datasets were collected, and where needed quality controlled.

Figure 15: Location of in situ sampling stations

Close-range spectral data (in situ reflectance data)

Spectral measurements of water, collected by automated TriOS sensors, obtained by NIOZ, at the NIOZ jetty station on Texel (NJS) for the years 2015 to 2017. This data is used for atmospheric correction validation of S2 MSI and S3 OLCI (level 1). The processing methods for these data can be found in the [COLOURS documentation pages](#) (accessed 18 September 2017).

Spectral measurements of water, collected with hand-held TriOS sensors, from the PhD thesis of A Hommersom et al, 2009. This dataset also contains the concentrations measurements (TSM, CDOM, Chl). This dataset is used for verification of parameter retrieval algorithms from spectral data (level 2). Detailed processing methods of this data can be found in Hommersom et al, 2009.

Spectral measurements of water, collected with hand-held TriOS sensors, taken by the INPLACE project. This data also contains the concentration of Chl-a, sediment type and benthic biomass.

In-situ parameter data

Laboratory data

For chlorophyll-a and TSM, measurements were retrieved from the MWTL data set via the Waterbase public web service for the following stations in or close to the study area:

- Bocht van Watum
- Groote Gat Noord
- Huibergat oost
- Rottumerplaat 3 km uit de kust

These data are lab analyses based on water samples taken during measurement cruises about once to twice a month and are made available within a few months of sampling.

Data from the permanent measurement stations

Data from the permanent measurement station at Knock, in the German part of the Ems estuary, were provided by NLWKN. The data are TSM values derived from an automated online sensor of turbidity that delivers data every five minutes. Data are available from 01/2015 – 12/2017.

Data from the automated measurement station at Eemshaven owned by RWS were provided for a list of satellite matchup times. For each matchup, data at a 1-minute time interval were provided for a time window of 3 hours around the actual satellite overpass time. Data include, amongst other parameters, Chl-a and turbidity measurements.

For water temperature, data from a number of online sensors in the study area, but also in the wider Wadden Sea, were retrieved via the Waterinfo web service. These data are measured at a 10-minute interval.

Data from IMARES

For a comparison of value ranges and spatial and temporal patterns, a report by IMARES was used (Brinkman, 2015). This report includes results of in situ sampling performed by IMARES in 2012-2014, including chlorophyll in the tidal sediment as well as chlorophyll, suspended particulate matter and extinction measured in the water column sampled at a number of locations. As these data are from different years than the data of this report and only the report was available, not the actual measurement data, only a comparison for value ranges is done with data set. Two of the pelagic stations coincide with

MWTL stations used in this study: station 1 is located at Huibertgat and station 6 and Gote Gat Noord.

Figure 16: Pelagic and benthic sampling stations in IMARES dataset

HBOTE in situ data collection

To increase the number of match ups between satellite and in situ measurements, and to measure also parameters that are not routinely collected in the Eems-Dollard area (CDOM, radiometry), Water Insight planned to join the regular sampling cruises of RWS when there were chances for match ups (i.e. on days with relevant satellite overpasses and when the weather forecast indicated a chance for at least partly cloud-free images). Several of these cruises were cancelled or changed so that we could not join, and the others took place on cloudy days. Therefore, in the end, Water Insight only joined one cruise on the 13th of March 2018. Unfortunately, on the 13th of March the cloudy conditions did not let us acquire a satellite matchup. Still, WISP-3 spectral data, salinity, water temperature and CDOM were sampled.

Ancillary data

As ancillary information, data from tide gauges was retrieved to identify the timing within the tide cycle of each of the satellite images.

4.2 Validation methods

As described in section 3.1, two levels of validation are applied: inspection of the atmospheric correction (1) and inspection of the uncertainty in water quality products (2). With the in-situ data which was collected in HBOTE, for most parameters both levels of validation could be performed (Table 8). As can be seen, only for a few parameters (PAR, CDOM, Kd and LST), there was no suitable in-situ data available of the area. For these parameters, only the atmospheric correction could be validated, and suitable algorithms were applied based on expert knowledge and literature.

Table 8: Overview of which parameters are obtained at which resolution, from which sensors, which validation data was available and which validation level was performed

Parameter	Low resolution	Medium resolution	Validation data set	Validation (level)
SST	GHRSSST	OLI	RWS	In situ vs satellite
PAR	OLCI	-	-	-
Reflectance	OLCI	MSI	TriOS at NIOZ (matchups only for MSI)	In situ spectra vs satellite spectra
SPM	OLCI	MSI	RWS in situ, Permanent stations	In situ concentrations vs satellite
CDOM	OLCI	MSI	-	-
Kd	OLCI	MSI	-	-
CHL	OLCI	MSI	RWS in situ, Permanent stations, INPLACE project	In situ concentrations vs satellite
LST	SLSTR	OLI	-	-

Sediment type	OLCI	MSI	Sediment atlas Deltares	Sanity check, comparison of spatial patterns
Benthic biomass	OLCI	MSI		

Validation of atmospheric correction

For S2 MSI and S3 OLCI, several different atmospheric correction schemes were applied to the satellite images over a water target. The validation was based on matching the atmospherically corrected satellite observations to in-situ measurements collected from the NIOZ jetty station (NJS) for the years 2015 -2017.

Validation of parameter retrieval

Scatterplots were made, from which statistical measures, such as correlation coefficient (as R^2), slope and intercept were retrieved. Also, time series were created. Time series proved to give a better insight in the variability, value ranges and frequency of both data sources.

5 Atmospheric correction

5.1 Background

Atmospheric correction in essence is the inversion of models that characterise the atmospheric optical properties and mathematically describe radiative transport through the atmosphere (in various degrees of detail). This correction is necessary to obtain the water leaving or Bottom of Atmosphere (BOA) reflectance of all water pixels that can be viewed by a satellite (no clouds interfering) that are also not in the shadow of a cloud. The main radiative transport processes are connected to groups of optical active components:

1. Absorption by absorbing aerosols and gasses (O₂, O₃, NO₂ and H₂O)
2. Rayleigh scattering by small molecules of non-absorbing atmospheric gasses (CO, N₂O, CH₄ and CO₂)
3. Mie scattering by larger molecules (aerosols and water vapor)
4. Polarization effects

In addition to this, scattering by ice crystals in partially transparent cirrus clouds and aircraft contrails, lens effects at cloud edges and “the adjacency effect” have an influence of the observed Top of Atmosphere (TOA) signal of a water pixel. Depending on location, time and topographical height, different mixtures of atmospheric optical active components and variable path lengths lead to different effects on radiative transfer. To estimate the true water leaving radiance from the TOA radiance one also has to take reflection at the water surface by sun- and sky glint and whitecaps into consideration. Underlying physics and an overview of NASA Ocean approaches are e.g. given by Mobley et al., 2016.

5.2 Methods

Usually the process to obtain the water leaving radiance from TOA radiance involves the following steps (the order of steps is somewhat interchangeable):

- 1) Select pixels that are in the water, not obscured by clouds, aircraft contrails etc., not in cloud shadows and not affected by reflectance of floating objects and emerging vegetation.
- 2) Identify pixels that are affected by sun/sky glint and whitecaps reflection and either discard them or correct for the additional reflectance.
- 3) Correct the observed signal for gaseous absorption using assumed values or external data sources for O₂, O₃, NO₂ etc.
- 4) Correct the observed signal for Rayleigh scattering using knowledge about topographical location, height and time.
- 5) Estimate the amount of water vapor and aerosol scattering per pixel (or per image) and correct the signal for water vapor and aerosol absorption and scattering
- 6) Correct for contamination of the pixel reflectance from nearby, high reflecting targets (adjacency effect)
- 7) (Optional) Couple the atmospheric correction to an in-water model to solve the RTE for the total water-atmosphere system and obtain optical closure

For the HBOTE project we tested the following tools/approaches for atmospheric correction:

1. Acolite (vanHelleMont and Ruddick, 2014)

2. C2X (<http://www.brockmann-consult.de/c2x/index.php/home/>)
3. C2RCC (Brockmann et al., 2016)
4. Polymer (Steinmetz et al., 2011)

All mentioned approaches have their shortcomings, such as: neglection of water vapor (Acolite), neglection of topographical altitude effect and adjacency effect (neural nets), less ability to separate sunglint from high reflectance by sediments, etc. Most processors assume concentrations for Ozone and other absorbing gasses.

5.3 Validation data

Data sources

The in-situ dataset we used to compare and assess the quality of the atmospheric correction consists of automated TriOS measurements of water, at the NIOZ jetty station on Texel (NJS) for the years 2015 to 2017 kindly provided by NIOZ. The location of the jetty is Lat 53.001707 and Lon 4.789045. The in-situ measurements come from a Trios radiometer measuring reflectance on the water surface every 10 minutes. The time span for matchup used for both low and medium resolution is 120 minutes. The processing methods for these data can be found at the [COLOURS documentation pages](#) (accessed 18 September 2017).

Processing

The data were used as provided without further processing

5.4 Atmospheric correction of the low resolution (S3) imagery

Processing

The Sentinel 3 OLCI archive was processed using the Level 1 data available at Eumetsat's website. First step was to remove cloudy, hazy, land and invalid pixels. This was done using the IdePix algorithm available at the SNAP 6.0 software (Lebreton et al., 2016). Finally, the valid pixels were atmospherically corrected using an augmented (improved) version of the C2RCC processor. At this point, the processing results in 300 meter spatial resolution, atmospherically corrected flagged data with water leaving radiance reflectance as units. No further processing took place as we were interested to assess the quality of the AC comparing with available in-situ datasets. For Sentinel 3 we have three AC methods that we could compare: Polymer, the C2RCC and its newly augmented version, AUG.C2RCC

Matchup generation

As matchups we define the data (in-situ, satellite or any other) that were collected the same date over the same area and represent the same values e.g. Water leaving radiance reflectance. To assess the quality of the AC we used the NIOZ jetty Texel (Lat 53.001707 Lon 4.789045) station for comparison. This station measures every 10 minutes. The satellite value extracted from a pixel location that ensured that no mixed pixels (land and water in the same pixel) were used (see Figure 17). The in-situ data that matched cloud free pixels were used with no processing or any other alterations. For 2017, 20 cloud free dates were

available for matchup.

Figure 17: Low resolution Sentinel 3 RGB composite. Mixed pixel at the Nioz jetty

Results

The results from three atmospheric correction (AC) methods, namely Polymer, C2RCC and C2RCC augmented were validated with radiometric field data matching satellite observations. These AC methods were applied to Sentinel-3-OLCI (S3) images over the Ems Dollard estuary and compared to matching field-spectra. Figure 18 and Table 9 show the validation results of these methods, polymer validation results were excluded as it yielded large MAPE error.

Figure 18: Validation results, expressed in MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error) values, of atmospheric correction for Sentinel 3

Table 9: Validation measures for the mean spectra for S3.

	C2RCC	Aug. C2RCC
Slope	1.2	1.05
Intercept [sr⁻¹]	-8E-3	-6E-3
R²	0.86	0.92
MAPE [%]	38.22	29.54

Summary and conclusions of the atmospheric correction of S3 OLCI over water

For S3 we were able to collect 20 Match-up images over 2017. These were processed with the CoastColour neural network AC: C2RCC, which was trained using global coastal observations. For S3 it became clear that the net should be retrained to take into account some calibration deviations of the satellite sensor itself: this version is known as the augmented version of the C2RCC. Our statistical analyses were done using rather simple indicators because of the low number of match-up data. Both the neural networks show rather high r² values and slopes close to 1 which is very encouraging. The augmented version performs better in the blue spectral range. The differences in the green, red and NIR range are negligible. So, the Augmented C2RCC was selected for further processing.

5.5 Atmospheric correction of the medium resolution (S2) imagery

Processing

The Sentinel 2 MSI imagery was pre-processed in a similar way as the Sentinel 3 OLCI. The processing differentiates in the AC, where the C2X processor was used for Sentinel 2 MSI.

Matchup generation

Same as above (S3 Matchup generation), the NIOZ jetty in-situ spectral data were used, matching Sentinel 2 images that were cloud free at the location of the in-situ station. However, Sentinel 2 has a higher spatial resolution (10-60 meters, depending on the spectral band) which let us extract the reflectance values closer to the actual station without risking a mixed pixel. For 2017, 16 cloud free dates were available for matchup.

In total there were 13 matchups between S2 MSI observations and NIOZ Jetty in-situ measurements: 7 for Acolite, 9 for C2X and 10 for C2RCC.

Results

Figure 19: Validation results, expressed in MAPE values, of atmospheric correction for Sentinel 2

Table 10: Validation measures for the mean spectra for S2.

	Acolite	C2X	C2RCC
Slope	0.54	0.9	0.69
Intercept [sr⁻¹]	6E-06	-2E-3	-2E-3
R²	0.99	0.98	0.98

MAPE [%]	33.45	26.00	38.02
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Acolite processor results

The atmospherically corrected spectra, using Acolite, are averaged, per band, and plotted against the averaged in-situ spectra in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Acolite: Validation result of mean spectra

Figure 21: Acolite: Validation result of actual spectra.

Acolite spectra are underestimated (overcorrected), in particular for 490-705 nm bands. Bands of longer wavelength and the blue band at 443 have less overcorrection. The underestimation of Acolite is about 54% (the slope). The RMSRE is 29% for all bands. This RMSRE is for the mean values, the RMSRE for actual values is higher ~52%. Figure 21 shows the validation per band (coloured symbol).

C2X processor results

The validation results of C2X for the mean and actual values are shown in Figure 22 and Figure 23 respectively. Figure 22 shows that C2X results are much better than Acolite, for the mean values however. C2X slightly overcorrect (about 10%) the S2MSI spectra, with RMSRE of 26% (Figure 18).

Figure 23 shows the validation with respect to actual spectra. The RMSRE is now 55% (compare to the 26% in Figure 22) with data points closer to the 1:1 line.

Figure 22: C2X: Validation result of mean spectra.

Figure 23: C2X: Validation result of actual spectra.

C2RCC processor results

The validation results of the C2RCC processor for the mean and actual spectra are shown in Figure 24. The figure show that C2RCC performs worse than the C2X for the mean values and for the actual spectra. RMSRE 66% for C2RCC actual spectra whereas C2X has 55% RMSRE.

Figure 24: C2RCC: Validation result of actual spectra (left) and mean spectra (right)

Comparison of methods

The mean values of the resulting spectra are plotted in Figure 25. It is clear from Figure 25 that only C2X

falls within the variability range of the in-situ measurements. In addition, the C2X mean spectrum has an apparent absorption feature at B4 = 665 nm.

Figure 25: Mean values of the resulting spectra. The dashed lines (u/l) are the upper and lower bounds of in-situ spectra. Aco stands for Acolite.

Table 11 summarizes the statistical measure of the mean spectra. Table 12 shows the same measures used in Table 11 but for the actual values.

Table 11: Validation measures for the mean spectra.

	Acolite	C2X	C2RCC
Slope	0.54	0.9	0.69
Intercept [sr⁻¹]	6E-06	-0.0023	-0.0019
R²	0.99	0.98	0.98
rMAD [%]	29	26	31

Table 12: Validation measures of actual spectra.

	Acolite	C2X	C2RCC
Slope	0.46	0.90	0.74
Intercept [sr⁻¹]	0.0008	-0.0023	-0.0023
R²	0.67	0.76	0.78
RMSRE [%]	52	55	66

Table 11, Table 12 and Figure 25, show that the best results were obtained from C2X.

Summary of the results of the atmospheric correction of S2 MSI over water

For the atmospheric correction of S2 there are several processors available. We tested C2RCC, C2X and Acolite. The tests were performed using the NIOZ Jetty TRIOS spectra for validation. Since S2 has a lower overpass frequency than S3, the number of match-ups is limited. (7-10 matchups depending on the internal data flagging criteria in the processors). This number is rather low to perform a good validation but the differences were quite systematic.

Validation was performed on the mean of all available spectra and on the single observations. For the means C2X performs really well with r^2 and slope close to 1. For single observations the spread is larger but still the r^2 is around 0.8 for C2X with a slope around 0.9.

C2X was specifically trained on extreme case 2 waters as present in the Wadden Zee. This became evident from the validation results. Acolite severely underestimates the BOA spectrum. So C2X was selected for further processing. For validation of BOA reflectances, significantly more in-situ measurements of reflectances are required, especially to demonstrate the robustness of a chosen AC over time and to evaluate possible improvements when the processors evolve. Such spectral data is also necessary to evaluate algorithms for water quality parameters calculations.

General conclusions and observations on atmospheric correction over water

It seems that the tools for atmospheric correction (AC) for S2 and S3 are still a bit in development, although results are converging. One can validate the AC-processors directly by comparing in-situ measured spectra with BOA spectra derived from the satellite images. For this we use mainly the observations from the NIOZ Jetty. This is far from ideal since the Jetty is close to land. A large satellite pixel will have contributions of land in it and a small satellite pixel will have the Jetty itself incorporated. The Jetty is located in the Marsdiep which is quite dynamic in terms of water flow, with sometimes water coming in from the North Sea and sometimes water flowing out from the Wadden Zee, depending on the tide. It is not clear when the sensors have been calibrated and what their general condition is. Still it is the best data available.

It is clear that future improvement would hinge on several actions, namely establishing and maintaining the quality of the TRIOS Jetty measurements (including regular calibrations) and establishing radiometer observing stations at least one other position in the Wadden Sea, preferably at larger distances from shore with a relatively stable water quality dynamics.

6 Parameter retrieval

6.1 Verification of the algorithms for Chl and SPM determination based on in situ reflectance measurements

As mentioned in Chapter 4, pairs of in situ optical data with simultaneously obtained in situ laboratory data are used to determine the suitability of the parameter retrieval algorithms. The optical reflectance data is processed with algorithms that can also be applied to atmospherically corrected EO data, and the resulting Chl-a and SPM results are compared to results obtained from samples processed in a lab.

Data

Data on concentrations of Chl-a, SPM, CDOM and other parameters, together with reflectance spectra (using a mobile TRIOS set-up) were collected in the Wadden Sea during eight sampling campaigns in 2006 and 2007 (Hommersom, 2009). In total 156 stations were sampled, with a distribution from the wider and deeper channels to shallow areas. Also, some stations were measured several times, to obtain an insight in the changes over the tidal cycle. We used this dataset as a first verification of the validity of the proposed SPM and Chl-a algorithms. The in situ reflectance data was, after quality control, re-sampled to S2 and S3 spectral bands, to mimic atmospherically corrected EO data from these satellites.

Methods

Based on literature, the Nechad-705 algorithm (Nechad et al., 2010) was selected to retrieve SPM concentrations; for Chl-a the Gons algorithm (Gons 2005) was found to be the most suitable one. These two were applied to the resampled in situ reflectance dataset. Statistical measures, e.g. root mean square of relative error and determination coefficient, slope and intercept of Type-2 regression, are used to assess the validity of the results.

Here we describe the goodness of fit (GoF) between measured and retrieved values using type II regression (Law 1997), the coefficient of determination, R^2 , the mean absolute differences (MAD) and the relative MAD (rMAD) in [%]. High accuracy in the retrieved values yields type-II slope $\rightarrow 1$, type-II intercept $\rightarrow 0$, $R^2 \rightarrow 1$ and $MAD \& rMAD \rightarrow 0$. The symbol " \rightarrow " means the value approaches.

Results

Figure 26 and *Figure 27* show the comparisons of SPM and Chl-a, retrieved from the in situ reflectance data (after resampling to S2 band, and after resampling to S3 bands), compared to in situ data processed by laboratory methods.

Figure 26, SPM retrieved from close-range remote sensing versus in situ SPM concentrations

Figure 27, Chl-a retrieved from close-range remote sensing versus in situ Chl-a concentrations

The validation of retrieved values is shown in Table 13 in the form of goodness of fit (GoF) values. From Table 13, Figure 26 and Figure 27, we conclude that SPM and Chl-a retrievals are comparable for both sensors (S2 and S3). Retrieved Chl-a values have, however, slightly higher accuracy than SPM, with higher slope ~ 0.5 , $R^2 \sim 0.7$ and $rMAD \sim 35\%$. This relatively large difference between laboratory and close-range retrievals is attributed to two main reasons:

- The algorithms were calibrated with measurements from areas/waters with different biochemical compositions.
- Close range measurements are automatic and contain errors that are not accounted for:
 - I. Specular reflection of wave facets that was not accounted for in the correction procedure.
 - II. Focusing and defocusing of the light beam at the sensor due to waves, which were not properly averaged.
 - III. Variable illumination conditions.

This variability is mainly attributed to the small footprint of close-range sensing, thereby affecting the retrieval of the (back)scattering coefficient, a primary input/coefficient to the Nechad-705 and to a lesser extent to Gons algorithms.

Due to pixel averaging, these errors are expected to be of less influence on satellite retrievals with, however, residuals can be introduced by spatial mismatch and atmospheric correction.

Table 13: Validation of retrievals from close range remote sensing.

GoF	SPM [g.m ⁻³]		Chla [mg.m ⁻³]	
	S3	S2	S3	S2
Slope	0.22	0.21	0.56	0.52
Intercept	11.38	12.08	2.11	5.39
R2	0.44	0.41	0.70	0.71
MAD	21.00	21.04	5.72	4.45
rMAD [%]	56.00	56.25	37.84	31.71

6.2 Suspended particulate matter (SPM)

SPM background information

Time series of SPM in the Ems River were presented in Spiteri et al. (2011) showing a profound neap-spring variation of SPM values and spring tide SPM values almost larger than neap tide values. In terms of long-term series SPM values as shown in Figure 28, SPM values increased rapidly after 2005, in particular within the Ems-Dollard and middle reaches. The highly elevated SPM values in the entire estuary, and an increasing gradient towards the head of the estuary. The SPM values in the outer estuary have decreased, whereas elsewhere in the estuary, SPM values increased. Brinkman et al. (2015) investigated the suspended matter during 2012 and 2013, the suspended solid concentrations showed a steady increase from the outer areas towards the Dollard, and the range from below 50 mg/l at location around Huibertgat Oost and went up to around 250 mg/l at around Knock and Dollard bay.

Figure 28: Long term changes in SPM values from 1988 to 2010, measured at stations in or near the Ems-Dollard estuary. Circle line: yearly averages, thick line: regression. (Spiteri et al., 2011)

Validation data

Data sources

SPM measurements were retrieved from the MWTL dataset via the Waterbase public web service, the permanent German station Knock and from the automated measurement station at Eemshaven (Lat 53.47439 Lon 6.82173) owned by RWS. Namely, the MWTL stations that were used are: Rottumerplaat 3 km uit de kust, Huibergat oost, Groote Gat Noord and Bocht van Watum.

Processing

No further processing was performed on these in-situ datasets.

Low resolution EO data

Processing

The SPM derived using the Nechad et al., 2010 algorithm applied to the atmospherically corrected flagged satellite data. This algorithm was used as it is without tuning.

Matchup generation

SPM measurements were retrieved from the MWTL dataset via the Waterbase public web service for the following stations in or close to the study area. The MWTL data are matching the satellite observations per date. Meaning that MWTL and Satellite observations took place the same day but still, with couple of hours of time difference.

The MWTL stations in our area of interest are: Rottumerplaat 3km offshore (Lat 53.5661111 Lon

6.5641667) where for 2017, 3 out of the 9 available measurements are matchups, Huibergat oost (Lat 53.5591326 Lon 6.6611988) with 6/15 matchups, Groote Gat Noord (Lat 53.3042912 Lon 7.1566596) with 5/15 matchups, Bocht van Watum (Lat 53.3506449 Lon 6.9099646) with 4/13 matchups.

Station Bocht van Watum is close to the shore so, again like the AC matchup generation, the extracted pixel (for all the parameters that derived) is at a location (next pixel) that ensures a pure water pixel (Figure 29).

Figure 29 Low resolution Sentinel 3 RGB composite. Mixed pixel at the Bocht van Watum

Data from the permanent measurement station at Knock (Lat 53.327143 Lon 7.030599), in the German part of the Ems estuary, were provided by NLWKN via RWS. The data are TSM values derived from an automated online sensor of turbidity that delivers data every five minutes. 19 cloud free datasets were available for matchup. The matchup here is defined by the closest measurement between Knock and satellite.

In addition, data from the automated measurement station at Eemshaven (Lat 53.47439 Lon 6.82173) owned by RWS were provided for a list of satellite matchup times. For each matchup, data at a 1-minute time interval were provided for a time window of 24 hours around the actual satellite overpass time. 71 dates were used as matchups for the period between 07/06/2016 to 18/01/2018. Similarly with Knock, the

matchups that were closer in time with the satellite observation were used.

Results of low resolution SPM retrieval

Validation

The dense data from the RWS in Eemshaven (Figure 31) allowed to filter outliers yielding a better validation results (MAPE = 20%) than those presented by MWTL matchup data (MAPE =53.51%) (Figure 30). However, there are two situations where in-situ measurements of the Eemshaven do not show any variability, (stagnated in-situ measurements are highlighted in red boxes). The outliers were not excluded, yet S3-derived SPM product are of high accuracy, with MAPE ~20%. Excluding those stagnated measurements will largely enhance the quality of GoF parameters, as follows: slope = 1.12, offset = -2.47 [g.m⁻³], R² = 0.93 and MAPE = 8.22 [%].

Figure 30 Validation of S3 SPM products using MWTL measurements. The GoF parameters of SPM are shown on the figure. The green measurements (Groot station) were excluded in the GoF calculations.

Figure 31: Validation of S3-SPM products using the Eemshaven data set. Outliers are highlighted in red boxes but not excluded for the GoF parameter calculations

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 32 shows example maps of low resolution SPM results, at two different moments in the tidal cycle. One is around an hour before low tide the other about an hour (depending on the exact location) after low tide. In both cases, a large portion of the surface are surfacing tidal flats, leading to no data values for SPM. In both images we see higher concentrations at the shallow areas, due to resuspension caused by the relatively high currents between high and low tide (Poremba et al., 1999). In summer, the concentrations are slightly lower (around 25 mg l⁻¹) than in December (around 40 mg l⁻¹), which can be caused by benthic biomass fixing the sediments to a certain extent, or some differences in the tidal currents.

Figure 32: Low resolution SPM map derived from Sentinel 3 with corresponding tide phase.

Medium resolution

Processing

As described in the low resolution section, the same algorithm (Nechad et al., 2010) was applied to S2 imagery to derive SPM.

Matchup generation

The same stations were used for Sentinel 2 matchup comparison as for the S3 comparison. As Sentinel 2 has a 10-60 meter spatial resolution the extracted pixels from Bocht van Watum are centred around the coordinates mentioned above. Same date between satellite and MWTL observations but there is a two/three hour difference between the satellite acquisition and the in-situ sampling.

Results

Validation of S2 with MWTL also shows that the derived SPM products do not match MWTL data (Figure 33). This is in contrary to Ems Haven matchup set, where high accuracy of S2 derived SPM was obtained (Figure 34).

Figure 33: Validation of S2-SPM products using the MWTL data set and the permanent measurement station at Knock

Figure 34: Validation of S2 derived SPM concentrations using the Eemshaven data set. GoF parameters calculated without excluding the outlier in the red box.

For Eemshaven, the S2 derived SPM product are of high quality, except for one outlier highlighted in a red box. Removing this outlier would results in Gof: slope = 1.09, offset = -1.35 [g.m⁻³], R² = 0.97 and MAPE = 5.02[%].

For Knock matchup data set we did not obtain any correspondence between S2 derived SPM products and field data (Figure 35).

Figure 35: Validation of S2 derived SPM concentrations using the Knock data set.

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 36 shows examples of medium resolution EO based SPM maps, for two different moments in the tidal cycle. In the first map, it is just after high tide for most locations. Therefore, no tidal flats are surfacing. The only missing data points are clouds. The deepest water ways are clearly visible with low concentrations at the surface, any transport of SPM taking place in these areas happens close to the bottom. In the most inland parts of the Dollard, outgoing tide has started, the currents therefore increase and cause resuspension: the effect is visible as high concentrations of SPM in the most shallow areas.

In the second map it is close to low tide, however, tide is still outgoing, which is visible by the ‘plume’ of high SPM concentrations that is visible on the opposite side of Delfzijl. In the most inner part of the Dollard, only a few pixels show as water, because in most of the area tidal flats are surfacing.

Figure 36: Medium resolution SPM map derived from Sentinel 2 with corresponding tide phase.

Discussion and conclusions of SPM retrieval

Here we discuss the most important observations and list the conclusions. We split these between those related to low (S3) and medium resolution (S2).

Overall

Figure 37: Overall accuracy of S2 and S3 retrievals of SPM

Table 14: Overall accuracy of S2 and S3 retrievals of SPM

	Slope	Offset [g.m ⁻³]	R ²	MAPE [%]	NMAE	RMSE [g.m ⁻³]
S3	1.26	-6.97	0.72	21.24%	0.98	6.14
S2	2.72	-32.4	0.33	45.05	5.52	16.86

The overall accuracy of S2 and S3 retrievals of SPM are shown in Figure 37 and Table 14. the validation of SPM products is performed for Eemshaven and Knock data together.

For the pelagic stations of IMARES, a comparison of yearly averages from S2, S3, IMARES in situ measurements and MWTL data is given in Table 15.

Station	TSM S2 2017 [g/m ³]	# of obse rvati ons S2	TSM S3 2017 [g/m ³]	# of obse rvati ons S3	IMA RES 2012 - 2013 [g/m ³]	# of obse rvati ons IMA RES	MW TL 2017 [g/m ³]	# of obse rvati ons MW TL

					3]			
1	12.3	24	11.6	70	~25	15-20/year	13.6	19
2	15.8	24	17.6	71	~45	15-20/year		
3	26.5	27	22.8	65	~80	15-20/year		
4	34.2	18	37.3	60	~200	15-20/year		
5	48	20	44.3	55	~140	15-20/year		
6	43.8	17	46.6	49	~175	15-20/year	211	19

Table 15: Comparison of yearly averages of TSM from S2 and S3 (2017) with IMARES results from 2012-2013 and MWTL data from 2017

While for the station with the lowest concentration, the values correspond well, for the other stations the values from S2 and S3 are clearly lower than the in situ data. There can be a number of reasons for this; in addition to differences in measurement methods and depth, it should be noted that the IMARES data are from several years earlier, and a certain variability between years is expected. Also, the number of samples for in situ and S2 are so low that it cannot be assumed that the data are representative for the whole year. The MWTL data could in this case include a bias, because sampling always takes place at the same time in the tide cycle. For EO it should be noted that the performance of the algorithm decreases at very high concentrations (Knaeps et al., 2015).

Low resolution

Validation on in-situ TRIOS observations (Figure 26)

The Nechad algorithm seems to perform reasonable between 0 and 20 mg/l. Above 20 the results seem to break into two clusters: one quite linear cluster where the SPM is underestimated by the algorithm and one where the SPM is overestimated. It is not very clear what both groups represent, it could be that one group is predominantly sandy while the other group is mostly muddy sediment. In the case of highly absorbing muddy sediments one would expect the reflectance to be lowered and, hence, the reflectance and derived SPM concentration to be lowered as well. In future one might consider pre-classifying the sediment type and apply tailored algorithms per sediment type.

Validation on MWTL data (Figure 30)

Also in this case the values below 20 are more or less on the 1:1 line, but the high values are severely underestimated in all cases. Explanations can be found in the fact that we allow a time difference of several hours, as long as the data are collected on the same day. This means that in-situ and satellite results could

e.g. be collected at entirely different phases of the tide. It is also probable that the periods of high concentrations (probably the falling limb of the tidal cycle) are rather short and can be missed easily.

Validation on Eemshaven semi-continuous sampling station (Figure 31)

The importance of simultaneous sampling is illustrated nicely in Figure 31 where we see many SPM results very close to the 1:1 line with two small clusters where the measured values are almost the same and the satellite values are variable. We hypothesise that this is due to a malfunction of the in-situ instrument.

Medium resolution

Validation on in-situ TRIOS observations (Figure 26)

Since S2 and S3 share a similar bandsetting for the spectral band around 700 nm the algorithm results for SPM for both sensors are practically the same.

Validation on MWTL and Knock permanent measurement station data (Figure 33)

For the two MWTL stations, the satellite-derived value ranges match very well with the observed ones, whereas for the Knock permanent measurement stations, values differ by about a factor of 4. This very high difference is probably related to the vertical distribution of sediment in the water column at Knock. This is illustrated by an example TSM profile through the Ems river up to Knock that has been produced by BAW (Maushake, 2009) shown in Figure 38. It shows a quite uniform layer of ~1.5m with concentrations of up to 100mg/l, below which there is much more variability with concentrations up to 800mg/l. The turbidity sensor at Knock is at 3.5m depth below asl, which means that is measuring below the mixed surface layer, whereas with EO, the concentrations retrieved are those of the surface layer. Therefore, it is not surprising that the concentrations observed are very different.

Figure 38: Profile of TSM values in the Ems river (from Maushake, 2009)

Validation on Eemshaven semi-continuous sampling station (Figure 34)

Although the number of match-ups is not so large due to the lower overpass frequency of S2, the

correlation is extremely good.

Validation at the Knock station (Figure 35)

Again, the Knock SPM values show a large variability. (Figure 39) shows the variability of the in situ measurements from both stations (Knock and Eemshaven).

Figure 39: Inter-comparison between SPM matchups measured in Knock and Eemshaven.

Both sites show similar large scale dynamics with more or less daily peaks/valleys. Peak occurrence at Eemshaven seems to occur earlier than at Knock. The Eemshaven time series is quite smooth with regular transitions from higher to lower values. At the Knock station the pattern is quite erratic with high peaks of very short duration. The range is also very large from about 50 to 300 in summer to 900 in autumn. The short duration of events combined with the large amplitudes make this station less suitable for point validation of instantaneous satellite measurements.

Overall conclusions

Based on especially the Eemshaven data we think we can conclude that Sentinel 2 and 3 data provide a good indication of SPM values in the estuary for those areas that have concentration ranges up to 50. Above that the sparsity of MWTL points and the high dynamics of the Knock data prevent a firm conclusion, but the satellites seems to perform well enough in those circumstances too.

6.3 Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a)

Background

To understand the historic variability of Chl-a in the study we downloaded measurements for 3 stations from the Water Base website (Figure 40). As we can see, the Chlorophyll-a concentration was commonly peaking in the spring season on April to May and down in the winter season. It is interesting to see that the Chlorophyll-a blooming started at the same time at all three stations in 2013, but in later years the blooms were out of phase. In general algae blooms were earlier in the outer reaches (Huibertgat oost) and later in

middle reaches (Bocht van Watum) and Dollard region (Groote Gat Noord), which can be observed in 2015 where the spring bloom peaks first at the Huibertgat station, and followed with Bocht van Watum station, and last at Groote Gat Noord station.

Figure 40: Chl-a phenology (concentration of Chl-a in mg/m³) at 3 stations during 2013 – 2016.

Validation data

Data sources

The aforementioned MWTL datasets were used, plus data from the permanent measurement station at Eemshaven.

In this report we focus on the results of the EO-derived data, and the potential issues on its quality. The in situ data is used as reference, and generally assumed to be correct. However, also the in situ data can contain errors. An example of this is shown in *Figure 41* and *Figure 42*, which show data from the automated measurement station at Eemshaven at two days that seems erroneous. *Figure 40* shows the longer term developments in concentrations, demonstrating that the 160 µg/l observed at the continuous station in November, or the 80 µg/l observed at the continuous station in April are indeed much higher than the expected amounts. The data of these days are therefore not suitable for validation purposes. However, other in situ data sources might also contain erroneous data which was not discovered.

Figure 41. Chlorophyll data from the automated measurement station at Eemshaven, 2016-11-28.

Figure 42. Chlorophyll data from the automated measurement station at Eemshaven, 2016-04-03.

Low resolution

Processing

The Chl-a was derived using the Gons et al., 2005 algorithm applied to the atmospherically corrected flagged satellite data. The model was applied with an adjustment to the chl-a absorption coefficient according Hommersom et al. (2009).

Matchup generation

MWTL data from 4 stations Rottumerplaat, Huibergat, Bocht van Watum and Groote gat Noord were used to compare chlorophyll-a concentrations. Also, data from the automated measurement station in Eemshaven data were provided for a list of satellite matchup times. For each matchup, data at a 1-minute

time interval were provided for a time window of 24 hours around the actual satellite overpass time. However the measurement that was closer to the satellite overpass was used for matchup. This resulted in 13 dates used as matchups for the period between 2017-08 to 2018-01.

Validation results

We obtained a few matchups from MWTL data for validating Chl-a. The obtained results shows acceptable accuracy for S3-Chl-a, with $R^2 = 0.65$ and $MAPE \sim 36\%$. Since the data is sparse, the statistics are influenced by the outliers.

Figure 43: Validation of S3 derived Chl-a concentrations using the MWTL data set.

Validation with data obtained from Eemshaven site shows that after August 2017, the Chl-a in-situ sensor is stagnated to values between 2.1 and 4.5 mg.m⁻³, red coloured data points.

Figure 44: Validation of S3 derived Chl-a concentrations using the Eemshaven data set.

The accuracy of S3-Chl-a product (without the red data points, i.e. data after 25th Aug.2017) is relatively high with MAPE much less than the targeted accuracy by space agencies (of 30-35%), with high value of R² (0.96) and a slope that is 13% off unity.

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 45: Low resolution Chl-a map derived from Sentinel 3 with corresponding tide phase.

Figure 45 shows two example Chl-a maps derived from the low resolution EO data. The top image was acquired after low tide, in late August. Tidal flats surface still in the inner part of the Dollard, and the areas around these show high Chl-a concentrations, caused by a combination of summer blooms in the water column and resuspended benthic material. The image of September 23rd was acquired later in the tidal cycle. The Dollard area is now also covered by water. The concentrations are still quite high because of the warm autumn of 2017 (e.g. KNMI).

It is interesting to see the effect on the pattern from this relatively small difference in the tidal cycle. In the first map, of August 27th, the high tide is coming in, leading to lower concentrations from the north-west

flowing into the deepest channels between the islands. This is visible between Rottummerplaat and Borkum, and between Borkum and Juist. Between Juist and Nordeneij it is already outgoing tide, showing a small plume of water with higher Chl-a concentrations moving towards the North. In the image of September 23rd, between Rottummerplaat and Borkum the tide is mainly incoming, while between Borkum and Juist there is an incoming and an outgoing stream, while between Juist and Nordeneij the water is only outgoing.

Medium resolution

Processing

The Gons et al., 2005 algorithm with adjusted Chl-a absorption coefficient as described in the “Low resolution paragraph” was used to derive chlorophyll-a concentrations on the atmospherically corrected flagged Sentinel 2 imagery.

Matchup generation

Similarly as described above, the same validation data from MWTL and Eemshaven were used to assess the quality of the Sentinel 2 Chl-a derivative.

Results

Validation results

Few matchups with S2 (<3) were obtained from MWTL data for Chl-a, therefore the validation for S2-Chl-a will be presented for the Eemshaven data set.

Similar to S3, S2 Chl-a retrievals are accurate with MAPE below 20%, high R^2 (0.87) and a slope (1.01) close to unity.

Figure 46: Validation of S2 derived Chl-a concentrations using the Eemshaven data set.

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 47: Medium resolution Chl-a map derived from Sentinel 2 with corresponding tide phase.

Figure 47 shows two example Chl-a maps derived from the medium resolution EO data. Both images were acquired during low tide, in middle-late August. Both images have similar value ranges and patterns with the August 14th image appearing with slightly higher values. However, as expected in such a short period of time both images have similar Chl-a.

Discussion and conclusions Chl-a

Overall

Figure 48: Overall accuracy of S2 and S3 retrievals of Chl-a

Table 16: Overall accuracy of S2 and S3 retrievals of Chl-a

	Slope	Offset [mg.m ⁻³]	R ²	MAPE [%]	NMAE	RMSE [mg.m ⁻³]
S3	1.02	-1.74	0.96	16.81	0.39	2.92
S2	1.01	-2.46	0.87	18.71	14.95	4.01

The overall accuracy of S2 and S3 retrievals of Chl-a are shown in Figure 48 and Table 16. The validation of Chl-a products is performed for Eemshaven data only. From the Eemshaven data we excluded the data corresponding to dates from August 2017 to January 2018. As it was discussed earlier (Figs 37 and 39), in these dates (Aug2017-Jan2018) the field sensor exhibited erroneous measurements.

For the pelagic stations of IMARES, a comparison of yearly averages from S2, S3, IMARES in situ measurements and MWTL data is given in Table 17.

Station	Chl-a S2 2017 [mg/m3]	# of observations S2	Chl-a S3 2017 [mg/m3]	# of observations S3	IMA RES 2012 - 2013 [mg/m3]	# of observations IMA RES	MW TL 2017 [mg/m3]	# of observations MW TL
1	9.5	24	6.7	68	~5	15-20/year	5.8	19
2	11.9	24	12.2	70	~7.2	15-20/year		
3	16.1	27	17.8	64	~5.8	15-20/year		
4	15.1	18	21.9	60	~6.8	15-20/year		
5	20.6	17	22.6	55	~5	15-20/year		
6	13.5	17	24.2	47	~6.3	15-20/year	7.8	19

Table 17: Comparison of yearly averages of Chl from S2 and S3 (2017) with IMARES results from 2012-2013 and MWTL data from 2017

While for the station with the lowest concentration, the values correspond well, for the other stations the values from S2 and S3 are higher than the in situ data. There can be a number of reasons for this; in addition to the differences in methods discussed below, it should be noted that the IMARES data are from several years earlier, and a certain variability between years is expected. Also, the number of samples for in situ and S2 are so low that it cannot be assumed that the data are representative for the whole year. For Chl-a, a bias can be introduced in the yearly average from satellite data, because more data are available from periods with clear skies, which are also the periods in which algae blooms lead to higher Chl-a concentrations.

From both SPM and Chl-a validation exercise it is apparent that S2 and S3 retrievals of SPM and Chl-a are reliable with S3 providing better accuracy than S2. The advantages of using NMAE over other GoF measure is also evident. For example, in Table 14 the accuracy of SPM derived from S3 is 5-fold better than the accuracy of SPM retrieved from S2. Similarly, Table 16 shows that S3 is 38-fold better in deriving Chl-a concentrations than S2, i.e. Chl-a are 38-fold more accurate when derived from S3 than S2. These result are logical outcome as S3's signal to noise ratio (SNR) is 7-foldes higher than the SNR of S2 at the green (560 nm) and the red (665 nm) bands. This difference in SNR reduces to 5-folds for the NIR band (705 nm). These three bands were used to retrieve SPM and Chla concentrations.

Although the validation of the satellite results is generally very promising, there are also some discrepancies. From the validation, also the differences in properties of the data series becomes clear. We will list the most important differences, with their respective (dis)advantages and reasons for differences, plus the possibilities of errors in the in situ data.

Differences in methods

Between in situ data sources, various methods are used, all with their own uncertainties. For example, for chlorophyll, MWTL samples are analysed in a laboratory (www.aquo.nl) with HPLC, while chlorophyll from a buoy is derived with a fluorometer. Before validation of the MERIS satellite results, these methods were compared by Sørensen et al (2007). They demonstrate that the variance between laboratories for coastal waters varied from 10 to 16% for HPLC and from 5 to 20% for the spectrophotometric results.

There are also intrinsic differences between these determination methods. For HPLC, samples are taken in situ, transported to the lab and filtered. Next, the pigments are extracted from the cells on the filter, and these are determined via liquid chromatography. In the process of transport, filtration and extraction, few pigments will get lost. The chromatographic method is based on molecule size, so that only chlorophyll-a molecules are measured. Because of the manual processing of the samples, the derived concentrations are vulnerable to random errors.

The fluorescence method that is applied on a continuous station, is fully in situ. A light signal is sent through the continuously refreshed water sample, and a receiver on the other side of the tube catches the fluorescence signal of the pigments. No transport, filtration or extraction is needed. However, calibration of a fluorescence sensor is complex, especially because they need to be calibrated for a 'matrix' of components, while the concentrations of e.g. SPM are quite variable in the Ems estuary. Also, biofouling can have a disturbing effect on these measurements. These issues would lead to an (increasing) systematic error. In contrast to HPLC, also some of the breakdown products of chlorophyll-a produce similar fluorescent light and will therefore also be measured.

This means that data from lab and continuous stations will not be related as 1:1. The satellite data has its own determination method, and uncertainties. The satellite measures light which originates from the sun, is passed through the atmosphere, through the water surface and gets (partly) absorbed by pigments. The remaining light is scattered on water molecules or suspended particles, and passed back through the surface and the atmosphere, to the satellite. Because chlorophyll-a absorbs at specific wavelengths, the concentration can be determined based on the size of the absorption dip. In contrast to the two in situ methods, the satellite receives information from the upper layer of the water, instead of from a specific depth. The light that is received depends on the transparency: the deeper the Secchi depth, the deeper the water column from which light will be received. From a validation perspective, this makes it difficult to compare the satellite results with measurements from other methods. From a user perspective, the EO results are received from the first optical depth (which is approximately $1/K_d$), and therefore useful for deriving primary production. The uncertainty of the EO-based results mainly lies in the atmospheric correction, because the atmosphere has the largest influence on the light that is scattered back towards the sensor.

Discussion of the scatterplots

Validation of Sentinel-3 derived Chl-a on MWTL data (Figure 43)

MWTL observations for Sentinel-3 derived Chl-a are quite dispersed but in the correct range. The slope is determined by the outliers. This dataset is too small and probably at some locations too close to the coast.

Validation of Sentinel-3 derived Chl-a at Eemshaven (Figure 44)

Besides a cluster of points where the in-situ data are much lower than the satellite results, most of the data points follow more or less the 1:1 line. The pattern we see is typical for a comparison of satellite results and in-situ observations of Chl-a. Somewhere below the Chl-a = 10 value in the satellite results, the Gons algorithm starts to underestimate Chl-a since the main absorption features shift to the blue-green. For values above 10 the correlation is similar to the results Gons obtained.

Validation at Eemshaven (Figure 46)

Again, we see one cluster of data points where the in-situ values are lower than the satellite results. The other points follow the 1:1 line.

6.4 Coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM)

Validation data

No validation data were available for CDOM.

Low resolution

Processing

The CDOM retrieval comes from the C2RCC processor. No further calculations took place.

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 49: Low resolution CDOM map derived from Sentinel 3 with corresponding tide phase.

As can be seen in Figure 49 the CDOM absorption in the Dollard and Ems estuary is much higher on the image obtained at December 29th, 2017 (around 1.5 m⁻¹) than on the image obtained on September 4th 2017, when the absorption was around 0.1 m⁻¹.

There are two major differences between these two images, which can explain the differences in CDOM concentrations. The image in December was obtained just before low tide, while in the image of September for most of the area it was around high tide. Also, on December 29th, 2017 the average wind speed on the day and the day before was 5 m s⁻¹, while the average wind speed on 3 and 4 September 2017 was < 1 m s⁻¹ (KNMI).

This is in agreement with what is found in literature. For examples CDOM and DOC Laane (1982) and Lübben et al. (2009) were found to peak in winter, when the CDOM and DOC flow from rivers and land runoff is high. Another part of the logic behind it is that CDOM in pore water (1-17 m⁻¹) is much higher compared to CDOM in the water column (maximum ~2.5 m⁻¹) (Spitzer, 1981; Lübben et al., 2009; Dupouy et al., 1983). Release of these high concentrations from the pore water during e.g. resuspension is expected to contribute significantly to the CDOM in the water column (Billerbeck et al., 2006, Lübben et al., 2009). Lübben et al. (2009) also demonstrates that DOM (the total of dissolved organic carbons, which includes the coloured CDOM) in the German Wadden Sea peaks just before and just after the lowest tide. This might be influenced by freshwater runoff, but CDOM is also found to be elevated at those locations where saltwater and freshwater mix, and phytoplankton might die.

Absolute ranges of CDOM absorption in the area are mostly lacking. Literature is rather old, methods are different (e.g. fluorescence) and/or not comparable (e.g. when DOM is measured instead of CDOM). Hommersom et al. (2009) show, based on a handful of samples from the area, that CDOM in the Dollard area (at 440 nm) was found to absorb over 2 m⁻¹, while the median absorption over the Wadden Sea area

in spring, summer and autumn was 0.64 m^{-1} .

Also, from the cruise that Water Insight joined the CDOM samples fall inside the range of the Satellite observation.

Medium resolution

Processing

Same as above.

Validation results

No matchups were available for CDOM. However, the samples collected during the cruise, fall and the processed satellite images fall within the same range.

Resulting maps and graphs

The medium resolution CDOM maps do not show very much spatial variability and also not much difference between autumn and winter (see Figure 50). The values are within the same value range as the low resolution data set, which correspond to know ranges and the in situ measurements performed within this project (see previous section).

Figure 50: Medium resolution CDOM map derived from Sentinel 2 with corresponding tide phase.

Conclusions

The CDOM concentrations are within the known limits and can logically be explained by generally known processes. However, there are no recent in situ data available for validation, so it is recommended to obtain these for quality assessment. Retrieval of relatively low CDOM concentrations in the presence of high concentrations of TSM and/or Chl-a is inherently difficult (Ligi et al., 2017), therefore thorough validation is necessary, in particular for the experimental medium resolution product.

6.5 Vertical diffuse attenuation coefficient (Kd)

Validation data

Data sources

At the same MWTL in situ stations that were also used for validation of Chl-a and SPM, extinction measurements are regularly obtained by RWS. Extinction and Kd (diffuse attenuation coefficient) are closely related. Depending on the method of measuring the extinction (and the used wavelengths), and the wavelength(s) for which Kd is obtained, there might be slight differences. Converting one to the other without in depth details about the specific optical properties might induce more uncertainty than just comparing the two. Therefore, we compared Kd from EO data directly with the extinction measured at the MWTL stations. Also, the yearly average was compared with the data from IMARES (Brinkman, 2015) at the IMARES sampling locations, as well as with the MWTL data where those are at the same location as the IMARES stations (station 1 at Huibertgat Oost and station 6 at Bocht van Watum).

Processing

No further processing in the in-situ datasets.

Low resolution

Processing

The K_d retrieved using the Gons et al., 1998 equation with the calibrated b_b from Gons et al., 2005. This equation was applied on the atmospherically corrected flagged data.

Matchup generation

The matchups come from the aforementioned MWTL stations in the form of extinction which we compared with the K_d from the Gons et al., 1998, 2005 equations.

For Rottumerplaat 3km, 2 out of the 7 available measurements are matchups, Huibertgat Oost with 3/14 matchups, Groote Gat Noord with 11/13 matchups, Bocht van Watum with 3/13 matchups.

Validation results

Slope	Intercept [m^{-1}]	R^2	MAPE[%]	NMAE	RMSE [m^{-1}]
0.4582	0.6171	0.4514	31.405	0.4723	2.3128

Figure 51: Validation of low resolution S3 K_d using MWTL K_d

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 52: Low resolution KD map derived from Sentinel 3 with corresponding tide phase.

Kd is a relative simple and robust parameter which usually gives good validation results. Here we have only a very limited in-situ dataset that indicates that most of the Kd values from S3 fall on the 1:1 line, with couple outliers (still used in the regression). In the future we may need to mask the parts of the Kd maps that are probably above water.

Medium resolution

Processing

The same equation as described in the low resolution paragraph above, was used to calculate Kd for Sentinel 2.

Matchup generation

Again, extinction data from MWTL were used, but for Sentinel 2 only one matchup was available.

Validation results

With only one matchup no validation was possible for the Sentinel 2 derived Kd.

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 53: Medium resolution KD map derived from Sentinel 2 with corresponding tide phase.

Overall results and conclusions

The Kd from EO data and extinction from MWTL had correlation but the outliers reduced the slope value to 0.45. The outliers probably come from the different acquisition time. The patterns in the maps are quite logic, with both just before and just after low tide low extinction in the most shallow areas. Those can be compared with the SPM patterns seen in earlier paragraphs, as SPM is the property causing the most light

attenuation in the Ems-Dollard area.

For the pelagic stations of IMARES, a comparison of yearly averages from S2, S3, IMARES in situ measurements and MWTL data is given in Table 18.

Station	Kd S2 2017 [1/m]	# of observations S2	Kd S3 2017 [1/m]	# of observations S3	IMARES 2012-2013 Extinction [1/m]	# of observations IMARES	MWTL 2017 Extinction [1/m]	# observations MWTL
1	1.1	22	0.9	67	~1	15-20/year	0.9	16
2	1.4	23	1.6	70	~1.5	15-20/year		
3	2.3	27	2.4	65	~3	15-20/year		
4	3.1	18	3.5	60	~7	15-20/year		
5	3.9	20	3.8	53	~6.5	15-20/year		
6	3.7	17	4.4	48	~6.5	15-20/year	5.5	14

Table 18: Comparison of yearly averages of Kd from S2 and S3 (2017) with IMARES results from 2012-2013 and MWTL data from 2017

The results from S2 and S3 are quite similar, both are somewhat lower than the IMARES and MWTL data for the higher value ranges, whereas the lower value ranges correspond very well.

Photosynthetically active radiation (PAR)

Introduction

Photosynthetically active radiation, often abbreviated **PAR**, designates the spectral range (wave band) of

solar radiation from 400 to 700 that photosynthetic organisms are able to use in the process of photosynthesis. This spectral region corresponds more or less with the range of visible to the human eye (Wikipedia).

PAR data (as received by the Earth’s surface) is calculated from satellite observations above the atmosphere. The general concept is that by measuring the amount of radiation that is radiated back from the Earth surface and the atmosphere, and by knowing the amount of radiation that is received from the sun at the boundary of the atmosphere, one should be able to calculate the amount of radiation that is actually received by the surface (Geostationary Radiative Fluxes Product User Manual, Version 1.6., 13-12-2017, prepared by METEO-FRANCE).

The difficulty in this approach lies with the handling of the solar and viewing angles and the amount of light that is lost in the atmosphere, including in clouds. One has to take into account that any observation above the atmosphere measures light that has gone through the atmosphere twice.

Figure 54: Atmospheric radiation transmission
 (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Atmospheric_Transmission.png)

To illustrate the processes that affect transfer of radiation through the atmosphere Figure 54 is often used:

this is the “Blue sky situation”. The red surface is the spectral distribution of light received by the sun. The light between 0.4 μm (400 nm) and 0.7 μm (or 700 nm) is called PAR. In the clear blue sky atmosphere PAR is mostly affected by Rayleigh scattering and water vapor absorption. In many situations that atmosphere also contains larger particles (dust, soot, etc) that scatter and absorb light, and thus also affect the amount of PAR received by the surface. The biggest unknown in radiative transfer calculations is what happens to PAR in clouds.

In the report PAR (Photosynthetically active radiation) is given as energy flux in the units $[\text{W}/\text{m}^2]$ Note that these have been derived from a satellite product that is given as Shortwave Surface Irradiance (also as $[\text{W}/\text{m}^2]$) with a conversion of broad band to PAR band (Papaioannou et al., 1993). In the land vegetation community light sensors are used to measure Photosynthetic Photon Flux Density (PPFD in $[\mu\text{mol photons m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}]$). A value of 4.57 converts $[\text{W}/\text{m}^2]$ to $[\mu\text{mol.m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}]$, assuming that the $[\text{W}/\text{m}^2]$ is for radiation from 400 to 700 nm. The spectral ranges in which PAR and SSI are measured vary. Depending on the required accuracy of the primary production model, the coefficients may need to be slightly refined, probably based on KNMI-Cabauw measurements.

Although the Netherlands is a small country, the amount of PAR received per region can be quite different. Therefore, instead of using the single point measurements at e.g. KNMI, it seems appropriate to use the spatial maps based on Meteosat Second Generation observations, especially when projecting into the future where the Dutch territorial waters will be subject to primary production calculations.

To illustrate the further complexity of the calculation of PAR one has to consider that part of the radiation received at the surface could be radiation that already was reflected by the surface and then reflected back to the surface again because of atmospheric scattering or reflection by the bottom of a cloud, etc.

To improve measurements of PAR from satellite images several strategies have been developed:

- Model the atmospheric transmission by guessing what is in the atmosphere: educated guesses can be made by additionally measuring in spectral bands that provide specific information on water vapor content, CO₂ content etc.
- Assimilate satellite observations of radiation with weather prediction models that allow a better description of atmospheric transmission.

For HBOTE we made an inventory of available PAR data from various sources:

1. The Ocean Productivity portal: The PAR data that is provided by the Ocean Productivity portal is based on VIIRS observations. The data is delivered as 8 days or monthly averages on a 1080 by 2160 or 2160 by 4320 grid. There are also historic observations based on MODIS and SeaWiFS, but VIIRS is the satellite constellation that is currently providing reliable data. The data availability seems to extend to 2017 but not include 2018 yet.
2. Broadband surface solar irradiance data based on MSG observations that have been assimilated in the ECWMF weather prediction model (in hindcast mode as reanalysis data). There is the ERA5 dataset which contains data from 2010 to 3 months from Near Real Time. It contains data at 30 km resolution for intervals of 1 hour. The data provided is surface solar/shortwave radiation which refers to an interval of 0.2 to 4 μm . There is the CAMS and ERA-interim reanalysis data coming at 80 km resolution.

These datasets also contain the broadband surface downwelling irradiation.

3. MSG observations that were recalculated to surface shortwave radiation. This data is provided by the EUMETSAT OSI SAF. The data is described in the “Geostationary Radiative Fluxes Product User Manual, Version 1.6., 13-12-2017, prepared by METEO-FRANCE.” The OSI SAF produces hourly and Daily SSI products on a distinct 0.05° resolution grid for MSG. The products are validated in the METEOSAT and GOES-E Radiative fluxes validation report. Without going too much into detail, the products are based on:

- Observations of the most suitable satellite
- A calibration of the satellite specific channel
- A calculation of the satellite count to a bi-directional reflectance for the considered radiometer channel
- A conversion of the satellite radiometer spectral filter (narrow band) to the broadband of the solar spectrum. This step depends on the satellite and scene type (vegetation, desert, ocean etc.).
- Simple models are applied to account for radiative transport through the atmosphere (clear sky and cloudy sky parameterisations)
- For daily products the hourly values are integrated over the day.
- All products are remapped using nearest neighbour to a regular 0.05° resolution grid and written into a NETCDF4 file.

There is a reasonable stable relationship between Solar Shortwave Irradiance and PAR (Papaioannou, G. et al., 1993) which was measured as 0.473 above an urban environment. For Primary production calculations at this point in the HBOTE project we recommend using the OSI SAF SSI data * 0.473 to obtain hourly PAR. If necessary, the conversion factor can be refined based on KNMI Cabauw data in future.

Validation data

The OSI-SAF SSI products are documented in the Product User Manual which can be found here: http://www.osi-saf.org/lml/doc/osisaf_cdop2_ss1_pum_geo_flux.pdf. The manual provides a link to a map of pyranometer stations that are used for validating the SSI products. Validation results are described in e.g. P. Le Borgne et al, 2006.

Low resolution

Processing

The download netCDF4 datasets were projected in WGS84 projection, subsetted and converted to PAR as mentioned in previous chapter.

Results

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 55: Low resolution PAR image

Figure 56: Low resolution PAR image

6.6 Sea surface temperature (SST)

Validation data

In situ data for validation of the SST product were retrieved from the Waterinfo system by Rijkswaterstaat (<https://waterinfo.rws.nl/#!/nav/index/>), which gives access to data from automatic measurement

stations. Unfortunately, the time series are not complete for 2017, because the system only holds a limited time period of archived data (which seems to differ per station). As the data availability is not documented, it was not clear that the downloads had to be performed regularly to retrieve a full year of data. In addition, data for the station Borkum were retrieved via the EMODnet physics portal (<http://www.emodnet-physics.eu/Portal/>). An overview of the stations for which data are available is given in Figure 57.

Figure 57: In situ stations used for SST validation

For validation of the low resolution data set, data from the stations within the study area were used yielding a high number of matchups (807). As the low resolution satellite data set is an aggregated daily product, the in situ measurements were also aggregated to daily values by taking the median of all measurements of a day.

For validation of the medium resolution data set, the number of matchups was very limited (14) when only using stations within the study area. Therefore, the spatial search radius was extended to include additional stations from the Wadden Sea (see Figure 57), resulting in a total of 60 matchups. As the time series from the in situ sensors showed a higher short-term temporal variability than would be expected (see Figure 58) and some quite obvious outliers, in situ data were aggregated to 2 hour median values before creating the satellite matchups.

Figure 58: Variability and outliers in in situ time series from automatic measurement stations (Top: Amelanders Zeegat boei 2, Bottom: Eemshaven)

It should be noted that the properties compared in this validation are not exactly the same: On the one hand, the spatial support of the measurement (the size of entity measured) is quite different: the in situ sensor measures in its immediate surroundings, whereas the satellite covers an area of 1km² (for the low resolution data) or 1ha (for the medium resolution data). On the other hand, the in situ sensors measure in the water column at a specified depth of 1m, whereas the low resolution satellite data set is compiled from several sensors that measure the temperature of a very thin surface layers and integrated with in situ measurements. The medium resolution data set is based on the thermal radiance of the surface, which represents the so-called ‘skin’ temperature, i.e. the temperature of a very thin top water layer of about ~10µm.

Low resolution

The low resolution SST data was retrieved from the Group for High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature (GHRST) Level 4 sea surface temperature analysis product (JPL OurOcean Project 2010). This daily 1km product is provided on an operational basis by the JPL OurOcean group. It uses satellite data from sensors that include the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR), the Advanced Along Track Scanning Radiometer (AATSR), the Spinning Enhanced Visible and Infrared Imager (SEVIRI), the Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer-EOS (AMSRE), the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission Microwave Imager (TMI), the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) Imager, the Multi-Functional Transport Satellite 1R (MTSAT-1R) radiometer, and in situ data from drifting and moored buoys. Data were downloaded as a 3 dimensional NetCDF file. No further processing took place.

For matchups, data were extracted at the location of the in situ station, except where those were very close to the shore, then the satellite data were retrieved from a point a short distance offshore. In such a way, 807 matchups were produced. The correlation between the in situ and EO data is illustrated in Figure

59, the corresponding statistics are given in Table 19. Overall, the data correspond well, with a good correlation, low error and only very few outliers. The overall good correspondence of the in situ and the satellite data is also illustrated in Figure 60 which shows the time series of daily aggregated in situ data vs daily SST data derived from low resolution EO for two of the in situ stations.

Figure 59: Scatterplot in situ (daily median) versus GHRSSST 1km data for SST for the 7 stations in the study area (2017)

Table 19. Statistics for SST retrieval for low resolution data

	R ²	Slope	Intercept	R	P	Standard error	RMSE
Low resolution SST	0.96	0.91	1.05	0.98	0.0	0.01	1.01

Figure 60: Time series plots in situ and low resolution EO data

The resulting maps (Figure 61) show a rather smooth variation over the study area without a lot of detail. They clearly show larger scale patterns: In winter (February, left map) SST is lower in the tidal areas closer to the coast, whereas in summer (June, right image) these areas show higher temperatures, which conforms to expectations.

Figure 61: Example low resolution SST maps (no corresponding tide phase is given as these are daily aggregated products)

Medium resolution

The medium resolution SST data set was derived from the thermal infrared bands of the TIRS instrument on Landsat 8. Landsat 8 data were retrieved from USGS Earth Explorer. The first processing step was cloud flagging with IdePix operator in SNAP (Lebreton et al, 2016). Then, atmospheric correction was performed based on the method of Barsi (2005), using the Atmospheric Correction Parameter Calculator service provided by NASA (<https://atmcorr.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). For the atmospheric correction calculation archived weather observation provided by KNMI were used (http://www.sciamachy-validation.org/climatology/daily_data/selection.cgi). The resulting surface radiance was converted to surface temperature using a single band approach (Band 10).

For matchups, data were extracted at the location of the in situ station, except where those were very close to the shore, then the satellite data were retrieved from a point a short distance offshore. The satellite-derived value was compared to the median of the 2-hour interval into which it fell. If there was no data for that interval, the closest time interval was used if it was of the same day. In such a way, 60 matchups were produced. The correlation between the in situ and EO data is illustrated in Figure 62, the corresponding statistics are given in Table 20. Overall, the data correspond well, with a good correlation, low error and only very few outliers. The overall good correspondence of the in situ and the satellite data is also illustrated in Figure 63 which shows the time series of 2-hourly aggregated in situ data vs SST data derived from medium resolution EO for two of the in situ stations.

Figure 62: Scatterplot in situ (2-hour median) versus Landsat8 data for SST for the 24 stations in the Wadden Sea (2017)

The correlation between medium resolution EO-based and in-situ SST is quite good.

Table 20. Statistics for SST retrieval for medium resolution data

	R ²	slope	intercept	R	P	standard error	RMSE
Medium resolution SST	0.97	0.86	1.23	0.98	0.0	0.03	1.07

Figure 63: Time series plots in situ and medium resolution EO data

Two example maps are shown in Figure 64 and Figure 65. They show both larger scale and smaller scale variation in SST. The larger scale variation is similar to the patterns seen in the low resolution data (see Figure 61). In addition in these medium resolution maps, smaller scale variation can be seen, which could be related to bathymetry.

Figure 64: Medium resolution SST map derived from Landsat 8 with corresponding tide phase

Figure 65: Medium resolution SST map derived from Landsat 8 with corresponding tide phase

Conclusions

In conclusion, it can be stated that both the low and the medium resolution data sets for SST show a similarly high accuracy when evaluated with in situ validation data. Also, the overall patterns of the two datasets match well (see Figure 61, Figure 65 and Figure 64). So the difference between the data sets is not so much their

accuracy, but their characteristics such as frequency (daily interpolated data available for low resolution, less than 10 relatively cloud-free images available per year for the medium resolution data set) and the spatial resolution (1km vs 100m).

6.7 Land surface temperature (LST)

Validation data

No validation data was available for land surface temperature.

Medium resolution

Processing

The medium resolution LST data set was derived from the thermal infrared bands of the TIRS instrument on Landsat 8. The processing is in principle the same as for SST (see section 0), except for a different parameterisation of the land surface emissivity.

Resulting maps are shown in Figure 66 and Figure 67

Figure 66: Medium resolution LST map derived from Landsat 8 with corresponding tide phase

Figure 67: Medium resolution LST map derived from Landsat 8 with corresponding tide phase

The patterns conform to expectations, with the shallower areas that are longer exposed being colder in winter and warmer in summer. The maximum temperature in June seems rather high, but without validation data this cannot be checked.

Conclusions

As there is no validation data available, it is not possible to give an estimate of the accuracy of the LST data. However, it can be noted that the algorithm for land and water surface temperature is in principle the same, because for the thermal emissivity bands that are used, land and water do not behave inherently differently (as they do for optical bands, where radiation is reflected or absorbed at the land surface, but can penetrate the water surface thus carrying information on the contents of the water column). The only difference is the emissivity of the medium, which is different for different surface materials (water, soil, vegetation). For LST, a constant emissivity value for the mud flats was assumed, which was estimated to lie between the values for bare (dry) soil and water. If sufficient LST measurements were available, it would be possible to not only provide accuracy information, but also to evaluate whether the accuracy improves when using different or variable (e.g. based on the NDVI value) estimates of emissivity (directly measuring emissivity is also possible in the field and in the lab, but as this measurement requires very specific equipment it is not a recommendation of this study).

6.8 Normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI)

No validation data available.

Low resolution

Processing

To calculate the NDVI we used the top of the atmosphere bands after removing the cloudy pixels.

Results

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 68: NDVI derived from Sentinel 3 and corresponding tide phase.

Medium resolution

Processing

Same as described above, NDVI was derived using the top of atmosphere bands.

Results

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 69: NDVI derived from Sentinel 2 and corresponding tide phase.

Heldere blik op troebel estuarium (HBOTE)

Figure 70: Zoomed in (Borkum) medium resolution NDVI image for 4 dates. Scale 0-0.5.

Figure 71: Zoomed in (Dollard) medium resolution image for 4 dates

Conclusions

NDVI on the intertidal areas is low but positive indicating sparse vegetation. NDVI is the key parameter that can be observed with Earth Observation that is used by our algorithms to calculate both Benthic biomass and grainsize. Therefore, in future, an effort should be made to validate the index with in-situ observations.

6.9 Benthic biomass (BBM)

Validation data

No direct validation data was available, but for a comparison of value ranges and spatial and temporal patterns, a report by IMARES was used (Brinkman, 2015). This report includes results of in situ sampling performed by IMARES in 2013 and 2014, including chlorophyll in the tidal sediment sampled in 6 locations (Figure 16) in 2013.

Low resolution

Processing

The Benthic biomass is derived using the algorithm described Kromkamp et al., 2006.

Matchup generation

Extracted the pixels that were not flagged out at the locations that the sampling took place. No further processing or filtering was done in the extracted pixels.

Results

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 72 shows the extracted pixels of benthic biomass over the year 2017 from Sentinel 3. And Figure 73 shows the in-situ sampling graph from IMARES. It can be seen that the range is similar. However, Sentinel 3 has a high peak in sampling station EDB06 around May whereas the highest peak for the in-situ data is around September in sampling station EDB05. Both these stations are located in the southern part of the Ems estuary.

Figure 72: Sentinel 3 derived benthic biomass over 2017

Chlorophyll-a in tidal sediment Eems-Dollard, 2013

Figure 73: IMARES in-situ sampling results over the year 2013 (from Brinkman, 2015)

Figure 74. Benthic biomass derived from Sentinel 3 and corresponding tide phase.

Figure 75: Zoomed in (Borkum) medium resolution benthic biomass image. Scale 0-200

Figure 76: Zoomed in (Dollard) medium resolution benthic biomass image

Medium resolution

Processing

Same methods and algorithms as described above for low resolution.

Matchup generation

Same procedure was followed to extract the matchups for the medium resolution sensor.

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 77 shows the benthic biomass derived by the medium resolution sensor at the same location where IMARES did their in situ sampling in 2013. It is obvious that there are a lot less matchups compared to the low resolution sensor. Again, the range is similar with the IMARES graph. And also, stations EDB05 and EDB06 show the highest values around June and August respectively.

Figure 77: Benthic biomass derived from Sentinel 2

Figure 78: Medium resolution example of a benthic biomass map and corresponding tide phase.

Conclusions

The benthic biomass is based on a published and robust algorithm. The comparison with the Imares report is positive. Both low and medium resolution benthic biomass products are falling in the same range. Moreover, the stations in the south, EDB05 and EDB06 yield the highest values as expected. The satellite results overall give a higher peak in the values. This could be explained by the sampling methods, where Imares sampled in different depths whereas we looked in the surface where the highest values are expected. Still, the in-situ sampling took place in 2013 while the satellite observations in 2017. Still, the range of the values and the values from each individual sampling station looks logic and in agreement.

6.10 Grain size

A simple and robust algorithm for detecting grain size indicators in the Wadden Sea and Dollard estuary was based on available datasets: “Sediment Atlas Wadden Sea” (This dataset is made available by Gerben de Boer as netCDF file in the OpenEarth Server at Deltares) and the bathymetry map for the area was downloaded from EMODNET (HBOTE report phase 1).

From the dataset we calculated the D50 value for all locations (D50 is the median grainsize (as phi) determined from the point where the cumulative Phi plot reaches the value 50. The median grain size is often used as an overall indicator. The approach to building a D50 algorithm for Sentinel 2 was as follows:

From literature it was assessed that topographic elevation will be an important factor in sediment grain size. The sorting effects of wind and currents will probably leave higher grain sizes at relatively higher places in the estuary, while mud will collect probably at the intertidal mudflats (as we also see in practice). It is also assessed from literature that bigger grains (sand) have higher reflectance than smaller grains (mud) because of the difference in material, shape of the grains and organic content. Grain size detection is hampered when vegetation is covering the surface. The problem with using the sediment atlas data to

device an algorithm is the fact that the data is quite old. Our first attempt to design a simple and robust algorithm was to correlate satellite observed S2 NDVI values (as a more or less constant indicator between images) and actual bathymetry to the older sediment atlas observations, hoping that the original distribution of sand/mudflats etc has not changed completely in the area. A very good cloudless image at high solar zenith angle (2nd June 2017) was selected to obtain NDVI values at Sediment Atlas locations. The Bathymetry map downloaded from EMODNET was also sampled at these locations. Unfortunately, although there are more recent datasets available at NIOZ, the project has not been able to get access to such data since the recent Sibes data have not been completely processed.

The following equation was obtained:

$$D50 = 27.31 - 1.55 * NDVI - 1.62 * Z$$

For the following boundary conditions:

- 1) $Z \leq 0$
- 2) $NDVI > 0$ and $NDVI \leq 0.4$
- 3) $D50 \leq 40$

Figure 79: D50 derived from one S2 image (2017) versus D50 from the sediment atlas

For interpretation purposes: If D50 is high: the sediment is mud and around D50=20: the sediment contains a small portion of sand. As can be expected from correlating the old sediment atlas data to one recent S2 image data, the correlation coefficient is very low (Figure 79). The equation is workable since it produces values in the expected range (mostly between 20 and 40). NDVI has a minor effect of the D50 estimation, the biggest contribution to the D50 estimate is coming from the topography component, which, in general makes sense. Wind and rain will move the smaller particles to settle in lower/sheltered areas; bigger sand particles remain unaffected and build dunes. This is e.g. very well visible in the “Slufter” area in Texel. Because of the time differences between the datasets, the D50 model needs revisiting in the future using

recent, simultaneous datasets of grain size, topographical elevation and spectral characteristics. The size distribution derived from the EO data compares well with the Sibes map based on data collected between 2008 and 2012 (Figure 80).

Figure 80: Median grain size of sediment taken from Gotje et al., 2017

Validation data

Data sources

To assess the grain size the “Sediment Atlas Wadden Sea” was used. This dataset is made available by Gerben de Boer as NetCDF files

Processing

No further processing.

Low resolution

Processing

The grain size is expressed in phi. The scale of phi is inverse to grain size. A phi of 8 or higher can be compared with a grain size smaller than 62.5 µm, which is clay.

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 81: example of a low resolution grain size image

Medium resolution

Processing

Same as described above for low resolution.

Results

Resulting maps and graphs

Figure 82: Example of a high resolution Grain size image

7 Overall conclusions and recommendations

The HBOTE project has delivered a substantial dataset of all requested parameters at the medium and low resolution. The objective of the project is to collect input data for the calculation of primary production in the area, assisted with Earth Observation data. [REDACTED]

[REDACTED] we cannot evaluate if the products are fit for purpose and can only comment on the quality of products by comparing them to in-situ data.

Table 21: Overview of data availability and accuracy for the derived parameters (“mean cover” is the fractional cover of the study area as described in section 3.3, “# of images > 0.5 cover” is the total number of images for 2017 that cover more than 50% of the study area)

Parameter	Resolution / sensor	Mean cover	# of images > 0.5 coverage	R ²	MAPE	RMSE	Comment
TSM	Low / S3	0.18	54	0.72	21.24 %	6.14 mg/l	Validation data: Eemshaven & Knock
	Medium / S2	0.33	18	0.33	45.05 %	16.86 mg/l	Validation data: Eemshaven & Knock
Chl – a	Low / S3	0.18	49	0.96	16.81 %	2.92 mg/m ³	Validation data: Eemshaven
	Medium / S2	0.32	17	0.87	18.71 %	4.01 mg/m ³	Validation data: Eemshaven
Kd	Low / S3	0.18	54	0.45	31.4%	2.31 1/m	Validation data: MWTL
	Medium	0.31	16				Not

	/ S2						enough match ups to calculate valid statistics, value ranges are very similar to low resolution
CDOM	Low / S3	0.17	48				No match ups, value ranges conform to literature values
	Medium / S2	0.33	18				No match ups, value ranges conform to literature values
PAR	Low / Meteosat	1.0	365				Validated standard product
SST	Low / GHRSSST	0.97	365	0.96	7.16%	1.01 °C	Water Info stations
	Medium / L8	0.52	7	0.97	6.58%	1.07 °C	Water Info stations

LST	Medium / L8	0.20	0				No validation data available
NDVI	Low / S3	0.04	8				No validation data available
	Medium / S2	0.09	3				No validation data available
BBM	Low / S3	0.05	8				Imares validation data
	Medium / S2	0.09	3				Imares validation data
Grain size	Low / S3	0.05	0				Sediment map Gotje et al., 2017
	Medium / S2	0.34	0				Sediment map Gotje et al., 2017

Table 18 provides an overview of data availability and accuracy as we have been able to assess it. In the TSM validation data, Knock observations have been included, although there is a large disconnection between the surface values as seen by the satellite and the Knock measured values at some meters depth. For TSM and Chl-a the MWTL values were discarded because of the too large discrepancies caused by time (and hence tide) differences. In general, MWTL data could be used to verify that the satellite results were in the correct range. It is evident that there is a trade-off between satellite resolution and coverage. Sea surface temperature validates very well using the Water Info stations and the PAR data is provided as a validated product.

In general, validation of satellite data with point in-situ data is a tricky exercise because one compares the amount of light collected from a surface (10-20-60-300 m diameter pixels) taken in a fraction of a second to a bucket of water taken at another fraction of a second in an area where water quality is never the same

from moment to moment.

The water sample is treated, stored and processed in a uniform and standardised way. The same applies (but differently) to a light measurement at the satellite. After processing, the amount of light at the level of the satellite is recalculated to the amount of light leaving the water surface. This essential quantity is used to characterise the colour of the water and to calculate the concentration of water quality parameters.

An essential aspect of remote sensing is that in one instance millions of samples are taken over large areas. This is something that can never be achieved by traditional in-situ sampling. All those millions of pixels have the same standardized quality and are treated using the same methods. The revisit time of a satellite is decreasing to once per 5 days at medium resolution to once per day at low resolution.

Tools for the atmospheric correction are still a bit in development but we have shown that if one takes the suitable tools for the water type under consideration, high correlation coefficients and good slopes can be achieved. The only comment is that there is only one data collection station for reflectance data which is not located optimally. We recommend extension of this type of measurements with 1 or two stations at suitable locations.

The atmospheric corrected reflectances have been used to calculate a number of water quality parameters, of which SPM and Chl-a as well as SST could be validated more in detail because some in-situ observations were present. Comparison with MWTL station data proved difficult because of the location of some of the stations and because there is often a time difference of several hours between the MWTL sample and the satellite overpass. This is a very complicating factor in this dynamic intertidal area.

It proved more fruitful to use the continuous measurements at especially the Eemshaven for validation. In a nutshell SPM validates very well, while Chl-a validates good above values of 10 and reasonable below. Both parameters appear in the same ranges as known from the in situ samples. Based on the strong relationships between SPM, K_d , turbidity and Secchi Disk we assume that those parameters would validate also very well. We see this in the K_d example, although this data is sparse.

From the reflectances we also derive CDOM maps of which we only can state that the values are in accordance with literature and historic measurements. This parameter is usually quite related to salinity in intertidal areas and we advise to sample both for further validation in the future.

Satellite images from S2 and S3 are very suitable for the calculation of the NDVI, which is often used as a greenness index on land. In intertidal areas the NDVI proves to be an indicator for benthic biomass and grain size as well. There was no direct validation data available, however, for benthic biomass, the value ranges and temporal and spatial patterns were compared to data collected by IMARES in 2013, where a good correspondence was found both in value ranges and relative differences between the stations. It would be interesting to do more detailed validation in the future, especially on longer term datasets.

Only very little inter-comparison has been performed between the results of S2 and S3 for the same parameter. For sampling points that IMARES used in their research in 2012/2013, yearly mean values were compared for Chl-a, TSM and K_d . The results obtained confirm a general good correspondence between the S2 and S3 results. Due to the relatively low number of available images from S2, these results are not fully conclusive, a longer time series would allow for more detailed comparison and analysis.

Figure 83: Average values for Chl-a, TSM and Kd for the Imares stations over the processing year 2017

Figure 83 clearly shows that, on a yearly average basis, S2 and S3 estimates of Chl-a, TSM and Kd are remarkably consistent, even though the temporal resolution is quite different and the tools for atmospheric correction are not yet harmonized. There is also a distinct gradient of TSM and Kd with low values on the North Sea side and highest values in the Dollard area. Chl-a in general also increases from the North Sea side to the Dollard area but here we see some discrepancies in the annual means between S2 and S3, especially at station 4 and 6. This is probably due to the combined effect of a different spatial and

temporal resolution of both systems.

Summarizing we would like to remark that this has been a very interesting project with findings that confirm our prior knowledge on the achievable data quality of especially SPM and Chl-a based on earth observations. The project team is confident that the products can be delivered operationally as batch or in near real time as service. During the operational service period we recommend to

- Continue the validation by increasing the quality and the length of the SPM, Chl-a and Kd dataserie mainly at fixed position stations
- To initiate measurement of reflectance with some fixed position instruments at strategic locations to further improve atmospheric corrections where necessary
- To measure CDOM and LST for a predefined time period at some locations where contrasting values can be expected
- To organize further cooperation with NIOZ to work together on validation of NDVI, benthic biomass and grains size distribution
- To intercompare in more detail and eventually integrate the results obtained by Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3
- To do more extensive analysis of the spatio-temporal patterns and dynamics based on the dataset produced

• To translate (un)certain requirements from the PP model approach into further product specifications for the operational service

• To set up cooperation with RWS/NIOZ to feed the operational satellite service products into the primary production model and to see how we can further operationalise the calculations for the client RWS

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